

**THE EFFECTS OF SPEECH ORIGINS
ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE LISTENING COMPREHENSION
ACROSS DIFFERENT SPOKEN LANGUAGE TYPES**

DISSERTATION

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**STATE UNIVERSITY OF MALANG
GRADUATE PROGRAM IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION
APRIL 2015**

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DISSERTATION
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by
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**STATE UNIVERSITY OF MALANG
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APRIL 2015**

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ABSTRACT

Syahid, Abdul. 2015. *The Effects of Speech Origins on Foreign Language Listening Comprehension across Different Spoken Language Types*. Dissertation, English Language Education, Graduate Program, State University of Malang. Advisors: (I) Prof. Ali Saukah, M.A., Ph.D., (II) Prof. Utami Widiati, M.A., Ph.D., (III) Prof. Dr. Nur Mukminatien, M.Pd.

Keywords: human speech, synthesized speech, Text-to-Speech (TTS), Spoken Language Technology for Education (SLaTE).

Aimed at investigating the effects of speech origins on foreign language listening comprehension across different spoken language types, this study was directed to answer five research questions. Firstly, do students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer perform the same as those listening to natural speech by native speakers? Secondly, do students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer perform the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers? Thirdly, do students listening to natural speech by native speakers perform the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers? Fourthly, does students' comprehension of synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer, natural speech by native speakers, and natural speech by nonnative speakers depend on whether the spoken language type is a dialog or monolog? Lastly, do students perform better when listening to dialogs than when listening to monologs? To answer the research questions, a true experimental, comparison group, posttest-only design was used.

This experiment investigated the listening performance of 64 sophomores majoring in the Teaching of English as a Foreign Language at a state university in Malang, Indonesia. From the accessible population of all the students taking Intermediate Listening course, they were taken as the sample based on the power analysis and sample size calculation. Taught by the same instructor, they were randomly assigned to listening to one of the three speech origins in delivering the two spoken language types.

The data of this study consisted of scores obtained from administering a foreign language listening comprehension test to the participants. Adopted from Section 1 and 3 of Official Sample Test 1 Pearson Test of English General Level 4 March 2011 version 1, the test comprised 9 dialog and 11 monolog items. The test was used as a baseline for developing two other versions. The speech origins of the two versions were Indonesian native speakers and a concatenative speech synthesizer.

A 3 (speech origins: synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer vs. natural speech by native speakers vs. natural speech by nonnative speakers) by 2 (spoken language types: dialogs vs. monologs) mixed between-within ANOVA with repeated measures on the second factor was conducted to examine the effects of speech origins on foreign language listening comprehension. The expected interaction between Origin and Type was not significant, $F(2, 61) = .46, p = .63$,

$\eta_p^2 = .01$, power = .12. The expected insignificant main effect of Origin was observed, $F(1, 61) = .28$, $p = .75$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$, power = .10, with no comparisons of pairs of means showing significant difference. A Games-Howell post-hoc test showed that the 90% Confidence Interval for all of the mean differences fell between -2 and +2, suggesting that the mean differences were small enough to consider equivalent. The planned contrast revealed that the comprehension of dialogs ($M = 6.13$, $SD = 2.27$) was better than that of monologs ($M = 5.36$, $SD = 2.03$), $F(1, 61) = 12.94$, $p = .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .17$, power = .94. The magnitude of the differences in the means (mean difference = .77, 95% CI [.34, 1.20]) was large ($\eta_p^2 = .17$).

Despite having different acoustic characteristics, the three speech origins yielded an equivalent level of listening comprehension. The relatively similar level of considerably sufficient FL proficiency could be responsible for the performance equivalence. Owing to the lower text difficulty, dialogs were easier to comprehend than monologs. The comprehension of the three speech origins, however, did not depend on the spoken language types and vice versa. The lack of interaction could be due to the spoken language type's more significant contributing factor in listening comprehension and greater power as the within-subjects factor in the mixed between-within ANOVA.

In future investigations it might be possible to include learner variables such as proficiency level and a larger number of the dialog and monolog aural texts. Future work examining both the speech origins and spoken language types as the within-subjects factors would also be of interest.

An implication of these findings is that FL teachers, curriculum and test developers should take the three speech origins into account based on the concepts of prescribability and switchability. Owing to the inseparability of dialogs and monologs from listening instruction, it is recommended that the difficulty level of the listening input be adjusted in accordance with the teaching and testing purposes. For the TTS developers, there is still room for improvement in dialog synthetic speech and user-friendliness.

ABSTRAK

Syahid, Abdul. 2015. *Efek Asal Ucapan terhadap Pemahaman Mendengar berbagai Jenis Bahasa Lisan dalam Bahasa Asing*. Disertasi, Program Studi Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris, Program Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Malang. Pembimbing: (I) Prof. Ali Saukah, M.A., Ph.D., (II) Prof. Utami Widiati, M.A., Ph.D., (III) Prof. Dr. Nur Mukminatien, M.Pd.

Kata kunci: ucapan manusia, ucapan sintesis, Pengolah Teks menjadi Suara, Teknologi Bahasa Lisan untuk Pendidikan.

Untuk mengkaji efek tiga asal ucapan terhadap pemahaman mendengar bahasa asing dalam jenis bahasa lisan yang berbeda, masalah dalam penelitian dirumuskan sebagai berikut: (1) Apakah mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan sintetik dari pensintesa ucapan memperoleh prestasi yang sama dengan mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan alami dari penutur asli?; (2) Apakah mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan sintetik dari pensintesa ucapan memperoleh prestasi yang sama dengan mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan alami dari penutur takasli?; (3) Apakah mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan alami dari penutur asli memperoleh prestasi yang sama dengan mahasiswa yang mendengarkan ucapan alami dari penutur takasli?; (4) Apakah pemahaman mereka terhadap ucapan sintetik dari pensintesa ucapan maupun ucapan alami dari penutur asli dan takasli tergantung kepada apakah jenis bahasa lisannya suatu dialog atau monolog?; dan (5) Apakah mahasiswa memperoleh prestasi yang lebih baik ketika mereka mendengarkan dialog daripada ketika mendengarkan monolog? Untuk menjawab masalah penelitian tersebut, penelitian ini kemudian dirancang menjadi suatu eksperimen telen hanya pascauji dengan menggunakan kelompok bandingan.

Eksperimen ini menguji pemahaman 64 orang mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris sebagai Bahasa Asing di sebuah universitas negeri di Malang, Indonesia. Dari populasi terjangkau yang terdiri dari seluruh mahasiswa yang mengikuti mata kuliah *Intermediate Listening*, cuplikan tersebut ditentukan berdasarkan analisis daya dan penghitungan ukuran cuplikan. Semua anggota cuplikan diajar oleh dosen yang sama. Mereka ditugaskan secara acak untuk mendengarkan salah satu dari ketiga asal ucapan ketika menyampaikan kedua jenis bahasa lisan tersebut.

Data dalam penelitian ini berasal dari skor tes pemahaman mendengar bahasa asing yang diikuti para mahasiswa. Tes yang terdiri 9 butir soal dialog dan 11 butir soal monolog ini diambil dari Bagian 1 dan 3 *Official Sample Test 1 Pearson Test of English General Level 4* Maret 2011 versi 1. Tes ini digunakan pula sebagai acuan untuk mengembangkan dua versi tes yang berbeda. Asal ucapan untuk kedua versi ini adalah penutur asli Bahasa Indonesia dan pensintesa ucapan konkatentatif.

Untuk menguji efek asal ucapan terhadap pemahaman mendengar bahasa asing, ANOVA campuran antara-dalam 3 (asal ucapan: pensintesa ucapan vs. penutur asli vs. penutur takasli) x 2 (jenis bahasa lisan: dialog vs. monolog)

dijalankan di mana faktor kedua adalah pengukuran ulang. Interaksi yang diharapkan antara Asal dan Jenis tidak signifikan, $F(2, 61) = 0.46$, $p = 0.63$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$, daya = 0,12. Pengaruh utama Asal yang diharapkan tidak bermakna ditemukan, $F(1, 61) = 0,28$, $p = 0,75$, $\eta_p^2 = 0,01$, daya = 0,10. Uji post-hoc Games-Howell menunjukkan bahwa Interval Keyakinan 90% untuk semua perbedaan rerata terletak di antara -2 dan 2. Jadi, semua perbedaan rerata cukup kecil untuk dianggap ekuivalen. Kontras terencana mengungkapkan bahwa pemahaman terhadap dialog ($M = 6.13$, $SD = 2.27$) lebih baik daripada pemahaman terhadap monolog, ($M = 5.36$, $SD = 2.03$), $F(1, 61) = 12.94$, $p = 0,001$, daya = .94. Besaran perbedaan rerata (selisih = 0,77, IK 95% [0,34, 1,20] tergolong besar ($\eta_p^2 = 0,17$).

Meskipun ketiga asal ucapan tersebut memiliki karakteristik akustik yang berbeda, semuanya menghasilkan aras pemahaman mendengar yang setara. Hal ini dapat disebabkan kesetaraan aras profisiensi bahasa asing yang terbilang memadai. Karena kesulitan teks yang lebih mudah, dialog lebih mudah dipahami daripada monolog. Meskipun demikian, pemahaman terhadap tiga asal ucapan tersebut tidak tergantung kepada jenis bahasa lisan dan sebaliknya. Ketiadaan interaksi yang bermakna tersebut dapat disebabkan jenis bahasa merupakan faktor yang lebih signifikan terhadap pemahaman mendengar dan daya lebih besar yang dimiliki jenis bahasa lisan sebagai faktor dalam subjek pada ANOVA campuran antara-dalam.

Pada masa yang akan datang, variabel yang berkaitan dengan pembelajar seperti aras kemahiran dan jumlah teks lisan dialog dan monolog yang lebih banyak dapat dimasukkan dalam penelitian. Penelitian yang mengkaji asal ucapan dan jenis bahasa lisan sebagai faktor dalam subjek juga akan sangat menarik.

Implikasi dari temuan dalam penelitian ini berlaku bagi tenaga pendidik, pengembang kurikulum dan tes. Mereka sebaiknya mempertimbangkan pemanfaatan tiga asal ucapan tersebut berdasarkan konsep ketertentuan dan keteraturan. Sehubungan dengan ketidakterpisahan dialog dan monolog dalam pembelajaran mendengar, tingkat kesukaran input mendengar sebaiknya disesuaikan dengan tujuan pengajaran dan pengujian. Bagi para pengembang Pengolah Teks menjadi Suara, peningkatan kualitas ucapan sintetik berbentuk dialog dan keakraban dengan pengguna sebaiknya diutamakan.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

This chapter covers background of the study, research questions, significance of the study, definitions of the key terms, and delimitation of the study.

1.1 Background of the Study

Second and foreign language listening comprehension is affected by many factors. In the past decades, those factors have been reviewed in detail by Powers (1985), Rubin (1994), and Bloomfield et al. (2010). From all of the comprehensive reviews, two factors always emerge, namely: the variation in the speakers and that in the listening texts.

The former factor is related to whether the speech origin is native or nonnative speakers. The above comprehensive reviews, however, leave another speech origin aside, i.e. Text-To-Speech (TTS) software that can generate synthetic speech (SS). After natural speech by native and nonnative speakers, SS has now come to play in second and foreign language listening classrooms (see e.g., Sha, 2011). This raises a question of whether the three speech origins yield a difference in the learners' listening comprehension.

The latter factor is related to whether the text is a dialog or monolog. Each spoken language type has its own characteristics such as definiteness to the

addressee (Murfit & McAllister, 2001), phonetic and discourse properties (Adell et al., 2012), and the continuity of speech stream (Brown, 2001). This raises another question of whether different features of dialog and monolog aural texts pose different comprehension challenges.

The speech origin is not a solitary factor of listening comprehension and neither is the spoken language type. Therefore, not only are the individual effects of speech origins and spoken language types worthy of investigation, the interplay between them on listening comprehension is also worthy of attention. Crucially, the focus of interest is on the context of foreign language (FL) learning.

Regardless of being outdated, a distinction between second and foreign language listening remains a useful framework to adopt. According to Rost (2011, 174-175), three axiomatic major conditions to learn a novel language to a desired level are language learning motivation, one or more capable speakers of the target language, and a social setting. Compared to second language learners, FL ones have fewer opportunities to meet the last two conditions. Learning to listen to a FL is generally limited to “*formal instruction in a restricted setting, with little or unsystematic conversational experience with native speakers*” (Best & Tyler, 2007:19) [emphasis original]. Worse still, even such experience has been by no means within the reach of many FL learners. Viewed in this way, the findings from the studies based on the context of second language listening comprehension should be kept separate from and not conflated with those in the context of FL one.

In such socially more disadvantaged context, permanent FL perceptual acquisition is more difficult. To solve some problems of FL listening

comprehension, some solutions have been offered. Renandya and Farrell (2011:56), for example, claim that some activities such as teacher-directed dictations or readalouds, purchasing graded audiobooks from international publishers, and trying online listening materials are effective in enabling students to develop fast automatic processing of oral language. The insightful solutions, nonetheless, may not be practical in all situations. The teachers' incompetence in serving as models (Saukah, 2009:9), unclear pronunciation/voice (Kikuchi, 2009:460), and common language errors transferred to their learners (Nel & Swanepoel, 2010:55) become a counter-argument over the teacher-led activities. An argument against the audiobooks and online aural materials is their incompatibility with the listening activities in the classroom (Sha, 2011:633). In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, the speed of delivery of texts is seen as the main contributing factor in listening difficulties (Graham, 2006:165; Jones, 2008:401; Lynch, 2011:81). The teaching and learning of FL listening seems to be caught in a real dilemma.

Fortunately, the speech by the teachers and in the audio materials can be replaced by SS. The artificial speech is generated by TTS software, also known as speech/voice synthesizer, which reads aloud and/or converts any computer texts into audio files. The computer program has such features as sound effect, speaker, language, pause, pronunciation correction, volume, pitch, speed, and export options. The features enable the teachers to "isolate, slow down, and manipulate listening processes in order to provide specific interventions" (Rost, 2007:106). The click of a mouse has now substituted for arduous costly conventional procedures for producing, editing and distributing aural materials. No studios,

cables, microphones, and speaker models are needed anymore. SS is then tailor-made for particular teaching and testing needs.

That SS is tailor-made for particular teaching and testing needs in the context of FL listening classrooms is on account of the fact that the artificial voice has approximated the human one. Such progression has benefitted from knowledge in computer science, statistics and signal processing as well as in second language acquisition, cognitive science and linguistics (Eskenazi, 2009:832). Today SS is mostly generated by using the unit selection method of concatenative speech synthesis. In this method, detailed voice recordings by trained speakers are segmented into such small units as individual phonemes, diphthongs, and even full syllables; the units are then chained together with very complex algorithms into a new, flowing audio text (Linguatex, 2009). In other words, the robotic computer generated voice created from acoustic data as in earlier speech synthesizers such as the formant synthesis has been humanized (Venkatagiri, 2010:42).

Until now the plethora of published studies examining the quality of SS in terms of accuracy, intelligibility, comprehensibility, naturalness, and expressiveness has fallen under three headings. Firstly, they were carried out by comparing synthetic speech of one speech synthesizer and natural (e.g. Hirai & O'ki, 2011; Kang et al., 2008; Kang et al., 2010; Kang, 2009; Mullennix et al., 2003; Papadopoulos et al., 2009; Pellegrini et al., 2012; Roring et al., 2007; Sha, 2011; Taake, 2009; Wester & Karhila, 2011; Wester & Liang, 2011). Synthetic speech generated by two or more speech synthesizers was also compared with human speech (e.g. Stevens et al., 2005; Syrdal et al., 2012). Those speech

synthesizers had either same or different platforms/trademarks. Secondly, a number of experiments were conducted by comparing SS of (up to) 20 different voice synthesizers (e.g. Handley, 2009; Hinterleitner et al., 2012; Stent et al., 2011; Stevens et al., 2005; Venkatagiri, 2005; Viswanathan & Viswanathan, 2005). Lastly, the evaluation was focused on SS of a single voice synthesizer, e.g. Chalamandaris et al. (2010), Francis et al. (2007), Handley and Hamel (2005), Huang (2006), Jones et al. (2007), Kastner and Stangl (2013), Lee et al. (2007), Roring et al. (2007), and Saz et al. (2010). The results of the studies demonstrate that SS has reached a considerable level of accuracy, intelligibility, comprehensibility, naturalness, and expressiveness.

The studies on SS also vary. Since human perception is not in a vacuum, some various aspects affecting the SS perception have been investigated. The factors include the effect of listener and voice's gender on social perception of synthetic and natural speech (Mullennix et al., 2003), signal quality and voice gender (Stevens et al., 2005), high-noise condition (Venkatagiri, 2005), age differences and speech rates (Roring et al., 2007), and simultaneous reading (Taake, 2009). Interestingly, a chimpanzee subject was able to recognize and report spoken-English words of two unusual SS forms, i.e. noise-vocoded, the noise-based input received by human cochlear-implant users, and sine-wave, speech reduced to just three moving tones (Heimbauer et al., 2011). Remarkably, personalized SS of a speaker diagnosed with speech disorders could convey many of his personal characteristics when evaluated by the speaker himself and two listeners familiar with him (Creer et al., 2013:1178). The SS development has managed to improve and remain dynamic even if today's SS is found considerably

satisfactory. For example, since 2005 an international event, Blizzard Challenge, has been held to better understand and compare research techniques in building corpus-based speech synthesizers on the same data (Carnegie Mellon University, 2009).

SS evaluations therefore have taken place extensively and intensively in various contexts: from phoneme to discourse levels, first to foreign language contexts, end-users such as teachers and learners to software developers, in both online and offline settings by using numerous criteria. Taken together, the evidence from those studies proves that synthetic speech has reached the level of near human one. In conclusion, the large body of research demonstrates that the state-of-the art SS is ready to be the counterpart of natural speech by native and nonnative speakers in the context of FL learning.

As stated earlier, in the context of FL listening the speaker-related variables consist of three speech origins, i.e. natural speech by native speakers, natural one by nonnative speakers, and synthetic speech. Yet, to date research studies on those variables have fallen into two types of comparisons only. The first one is the comparison between SS by a speech synthesizer and natural speech by native speakers while the second one is that between natural speech by native speakers and natural one by nonnative speakers. The following is previous work addressing both comparisons in the context of FL listening comprehension.

Most of the studies into the comparison between SS by one or more speech synthesizers and natural speech by native speakers as outlined before neither specifically related to the FL learning nor involve FL listeners. Only a few studies (Kang, 2009; Hirai & O'ki, 2011; Sha, 2011) shed light on the use of SS in the

domain of FL listening. Firstly, Kang (2009) conducted four experiments with university students and another one with high school teachers. The students took a dictation test of several synthetic and natural voice utterances and then evaluated the sounds on a 5-point scale. The teachers, on the other hand, completed the second part only. The results suggest that some synthetic voices had the same quality as natural voices for both the students and teachers but the teachers evaluated the synthetic samples more positively than the students did.

Those studies are very plausible. Kang, however, seems to mix intelligibility, which measures how every single word is recognized (Taylor, 2009:48), and comprehension, which measures how well a listener identifies the intended meaning of spoken communication (Richards & Schmidt, 2010:108) [cf. Smith & Nelson, 1985:334]. In most FL listening tests and daily lives, “we get the ‘gist’ of a message and miss some parts and this may be acceptable” (Taylor, 2009:523). The study appears to disregard the issue of comparative comprehension of SS and natural speech by native speakers in the context of FL listening instruction and assessment.

Another study was endorsed by a researcher’s wide experience of working with different TTS. Sha (2011) developed SS-based audio materials for the classroom procedure and listening tests. He found no evidence of decline in the students and teachers’ impressions of the voices as well as the students’ average performance and test scores compared with those of earlier sessions and tests using pre-recorded natural speech. Despite the innovative endeavors, the study provided no justification for a long temporal range of the two speech origins and

no further explanation of the issue of the comparative comprehension. The picture of the comprehension thus appears still incomplete.

Fortunately, the third study was focused on comprehension and naturalness. In two experiments, Hirai and O'ki (2011) compared the two traits of synthetic speech by Japanese TTS software and natural one by American English native speakers. A multiple-choice test was administered to measure the comprehension while a questionnaire was to measure the naturalness in terms of prosody, segmental pronunciation, speech rate, content plausibility, and preference. At first, no significant difference was found in the comprehension and preference between synthetic and natural speech. Afterwards, the second experiment was conducted for other participants having no prior experience to SS but different proficiency levels based on the results of a dictation test. The results suggest both groups performed similarly on both speech types. However, in contrast to the earlier finding, SS was less comprehensible than natural speech. No prior exposure to SS could account for such contrary results. Moreover, the upper proficiency group outperforms the lower one. In relation to the questionnaire, both groups perceived synthetic speech as natural as that of human.

These perceptual findings reveal the synthetic speech is as comprehensible as natural speech in the context of FL listening comprehension. In the following years, SS is likely to become inseparable from FL learning, particularly FL listening. In light of recent advancement of TTS technology, its potential benefits, and the increased use of educational technology, the comprehension of SS is of interest to dig up. Another reason for considering this specific area is the fact that the main users of SS in Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) are the

learners of non-native speakers of the language spoken by the TTS synthesis system (Handley, 2009:909). To conclude with, the use of SS warrants further exploration in order to be pedagogically justified, particularly in FL listening classrooms.

As well as the comparison between synthetic and natural speech by native speakers, another comparison has been made between native and nonnative speech. Both speech origins are commonly used in the teaching and testing of FL listening comprehension. The use of nonnative speech seems unavoidable due to primarily its practicality, i.e. the lack of native voice talents in FL education (Kang et al., 2008:98; Sha, 2011:633). There has also been growing acknowledgement of “the existence of the huge number of non-native English speakers and the need to incorporate their voices into mainstream English language teaching and language testing” (Llurda, 2004:315), and the fact that non-native English speakers constitute the majority of English language teachers worldwide (Moussu & Llurda, 2008:315). The inevitable existence of nonnative speech in FL education is thus generally acceptable.

The speech by nonnative speakers of the target language is dissimilar to that by native speakers. Because of local linguistic and cultural influences, spoken English by both speakers differs in characteristic accents, syntactic structures, lexis, and pragmatic features (Jenkins, 2006:42). The difference in speech sounds produced by native and nonnative speakers, for example, results from the nonnative speakers’ use of phonetic category assimilation or category dissimilation of the native and target languages (Flege et al., 2003:469-470).

The interaction between the two languages takes place not only when speaking but also when listening to a nonnative language. Drawing on a large of body of research into language processing, Cutlers (2001) has reached the conclusion that the listeners employ phonologically language-specific procedures for segmenting speech as used in their native languages. The conclusion lends itself well to not only the perspective of cross-linguistic speech perception which is based on the principles of the native language transfer and the familiarity with an accent but also that of World Englishes in which common native language results in common pronunciation norms (Harding, 2011:165).

For nonnative listeners, speech by nonnative speakers who share the same native language may be easier to comprehend. Such advantage of the common linguistic backgrounds between the listeners and speakers is termed “matched interlanguage speech intelligibility benefit” (Bent & Bradlow, 2003:1607), further elaborated as “an interlanguage speech intelligibility benefit for talkers” (Hayes-Harb, 2008:665). Much work on the effect of different accents entailed in native and nonnative speech on listening comprehension has been carried out, yet the findings seem contradictory with the above assumption. Major et al. (2002) rigorously measured whether native English speaking and nonnative listeners experienced less difficulty listening to speakers who shared the native language. In the study, the input for the listening test was provided by one female and one male native speakers of standard American English, Chinese, Japanese and Spanish. The English speakers had been employed as voice talents by an internationally recognized test publisher. The selection of six other speakers, on the other hand, was based on their acceptable accents that corresponded to a score

of 50–55 on the Test of Spoken English (TSE) and their ratings of a 5-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (*very heavy accent*) to 5 (*no accent*) given by 76 native English speaking university students. The results indicate that both native and nonnative listeners scored significantly lower when listening to nonnative speakers of English, Spanish native speakers scored significantly higher when listening to Spanish-accented speech, and Chinese native speakers scored significantly lower when listening to Chinese-accented speech. Thus, the listeners do not always perform significantly better on a listening comprehension test when the speakers share their native languages and neither are phonological characteristics in nonnative speech always advantageous to the nonnative listeners.

The global nature of English has resulted in different accents. They can be recognized in terms of regional (e.g. Southern American English), ethnic (e.g. African American English), and international (e.g. Australian English and subcontinental Indian English) accents. Major et al. (2005) then investigated the effects of all of the English accents on listening comprehension by using Standard American English as a baseline. In this study, except the speakers of Standard American English, the 12 other speakers had fulfilled four criteria. Firstly, the speakers had to sound like a genuine speaker of a given dialect. Secondly, they had to sound conversational. They also had to be fluent in handling the terminology of the scripts, thus appearing to be an expert in the field of the topic being lectured. Lastly, they had to have the appropriately mature voice quality characteristics for a professional or academic speaker. The results show different accents posed different difficulties to nonnative listeners of different linguistic,

national, and educational backgrounds. However, the study did not confirm that English nonnative speech was easier for nonnative listeners to comprehend. The listeners had greater difficulty comprehending the ethnic and international dialects of English than Standard American English, but not with the regional dialect of English. The reason for the results was mostly the familiarity of the nonnative listeners with Standard American English used in their TOEFL preparations.

More recently, three studies have provided further evidence that listening comprehension is not always attributable to English native and nonnative speech. Barlow (2009:4) found no significant difference in listening performance among 108 Emirian university students when listening to six different speakers representing male and female English, Arabic, and Chinese accents. The native Egyptian Arabic and Chinese speakers of English in this study were similar in age (45-55 years), level of education (MA+), years of teaching experience (10 or more), and IELTS pronunciation levels (5.0 to 6.0).

An additional support to the above finding was provided in Harding's (2011) study. He thoroughly measured English listening performance of participants of British English, Mandarin Chinese and Japanese native speakers. They completed a listening test featuring an Australian English-accented speaker, a Japanese-accented speaker and a Mandarin Chinese-accented speaker. Each speaker of a particular accent group was selected according to three criteria, i.e. having equivalent levels of general intelligibility, being reasonably easy to understand, and having identifiable accent of the native language. The results indicate that Japanese participants comprehended better a small number of items on the test featuring the Japanese-accented speaker Japanese but Mandarin

Chinese participants comprehend better several items featuring a Mandarin Chinese native speaker.

The results were further strengthened in the third study. Importantly, the study targeted two contexts of language use, i.e. English as a Foreign Language and English as a Second Language. The former context was represented by Sri Lankan test takers whereas the latter one was by Korean and Brazilian test takers. The speakers who delivered the listening input were two American English, two Chinese, one Korean, and one Sri Lankan native speakers. Except the American English native speakers, the other ones had obtained both the Test of Spoken English (TSE) and Spoken Proficiency English Assessment (SPEAK) scores of at least 50 out of 60 score points. That under no circumstances did nonnative speech types make test takers perform differently in a listening comprehension test consisting of standard American along with Chinese, Korean, and Sri Lankan accented English resulted in “Yes” to answer ‘Why not non-native varieties of English as listening comprehension test input?’ (Abeywickrama, 2013:69). As indicated by the above studies, English native speech does not always hinder English as a second and/or foreign language learners’ listening success and neither do the shared native accents benefit them.

The findings on the two types of comparisons show that synthetic speech is as comprehensible as natural one by native speakers and that natural speech by native speakers is as comprehensible as natural speech by nonnative speakers. However, there is still a need for investigating the effect of the three speech origins on FL listening comprehension as called for by Kang et al. (2008:105).

Fitting them all together is pertinently a challenging area in the fields of Natural Language Generation, Spoken Language Technology for Education (SLaTE), CALL, and FL teaching learning. In the first field, the current knowledge of how well SS can be comprehended has as yet been largely based on the data from the comparison between SS and natural speech by native speakers of a particular language of which the SS is developed. In the last three fields, this study extends the wider use of synthetic speech in FL learning on a scientific basis. This study is therefore possibly among the first steps towards enhancing the understanding of relative comprehension of the three speech origins in FL education.

To further the effects of the three origins of speech, it is unavoidable to raise a question of their effects across different spoken language types. In this study, the focus of interest was the types of oral language entailed in the teaching and testing of listening, i.e. dialogs and monologs. In the context of this study, a dialog text was delivered by both a female and a male speakers giving and/or exchanging information, whereas a monolog one was delivered by either a female or a male speaker giving information. Other terms referring to the same spoken language types are lectures and conversations (Educational Testing Service, 2009:123), read aloud and conversational speech (Andersson et al., 2012:176), or fluent/reading-style and disfluent/talking-style speech (Adell et al., 2012:459-460). The big picture of the above types of oral language has been clearly drawn by Brown (2001:250-251).

Portraying dialog and monolog texts is one of the efforts to provide a full account of a language. As Crystals (1970) writes, comprehending the differences

between the dialog and monolog texts as the two methods of communicating information carries with it “the whole complex of varieties and styles that make up 'a' language” (p. 99). In her seminal work, Fox Tree (1999:40) presented the collaborative theory of communication that held two contradictory hypotheses, i.e. a monologue text conveyed information better because of providing more detailed information and being free from the messiness of dialog such as overlapped speech but a dialog text eased comprehension because of containing participating addressees’ perspectives and feedback. Taking the theory as a starting point, she had the participants listen to monolog and dialog recordings that described some abstract shapes or tangrams figures. As overhearers, they extracted information better from dialog texts even though many of them who had performed better on the dialog found the dialogs more difficult because of being desultory and overly repetitive along with having too many interruptions and distracting chatter. Two possible explanations were pointed out for the findings, i.e. the high frequency of discourse markers and multiple perspectives in a dialog (Fox Tree, 1999). The former helped not only speakers structure their descriptions but also, as the marks of transitions, listeners followed the speakers more easily whereas the latter increased the listeners’ chance to adopt one of the perspective.

Since then the comparison between the dialog and monolog aural texts has gained much more attention. As a continuation of the above collaborative theory, when examining the effects of production variables in monolog and dialog texts on comprehension by novel listeners, Murfitt and McAllister (2001) found that, when producing dialogs, the speakers tailored their utterances such as definiteness to their addressees. The combined production variables thus did have significant

effect on the listeners' better comprehension on dialog texts. That multiple perspectives is the main factor that make dialog texts convey information better has been concluded by Pickering and Garrod (2004); Fox Tree and Mayer (2008); and Branigan et al. (2011). Therefore, there is widespread agreement that dialog spoken texts are better comprehended than monolog ones.

With regard to spoken language technology, the high standard intelligibility and naturalness of monolog SS seems inadequate since the various applications of TTS systems such as video games and multilingual broadcasting demand more than just information reading. The quality gap may be attributable to the language differences between read aloud and conversational speech in content, structure, along with phonetic and discourse properties such as filled pauses, discourse markers, and backchannels (Adell et al., 2012:176). The specific characteristics of a dialog text present a challenge for the research area of Natural Language Generation. For this reason, until now filmmakers have not replaced natural speech voices with computer-generated speech (Sha, 2011:640). No speech synthesizers have been given a credit even in computer-animated movies in which human movie stars play no role.

Intensive research into how to produce dialog SS has been underway in order to draw level with the quality of monolog SS. For example, to generate dialog SS from written monologs, Piwek and Svetlana (2010:1) constructed semi-automatic M2D (Monolog to Dialog) generation rules based on a parallel corpus of dialogs and monologs expressing the same information to generate dialog SS from written monologs. Despite this interest, one of the main issues in the generation of the dialog synthetic speech for end users is a lack of user-

friendliness. In his own exploration of some TTS software packages such as IVO Software, it seems to the experimenter that they have not facilitated the production of dialogic SS by Graphical User Interface (GUI) yet, even if they provide female and male voices. In this study, using Voice Reader Studio (Linguattec, 2014), the experimenter had to manually insert the command tags directly into the source text to structure the audio output of dialog text files such as the turns of female and male speech.

Since the main focus of interest at spoken language technology apparently seems to be on the generation of dialog utterance, the issue of the relative comprehension between monolog SS either by female or male speech and dialog one both by female and male speech has been overlooked. To make matters worse, the comparison between dialog and monolog SS in the field of FL listening comprehension is possibly not widely found. Despite this, since the generation of dialog synthetic speech is not mature as fully as that of monolog one, it can thus be reasonably assumed that FL learners will comprehend monolog synthetic speech better than dialog one.

Monolog and dialog audio texts are universally acknowledged in the teaching and testing of FL listening comprehension. Nonetheless, unlike considerable attention paid to the difference between dialog and monolog audio texts by other realms such as psychology as reviewed above, only a small body of research attempts to understand which spoken language type is easier to comprehend in the enterprise of FL teaching. As Bloomfield et al. (2010:41-44) write, many studies tend to focus on the effect of such factors correlated with different styles of monolog text as orality and rhetorical structure on listening

comprehension. Even researchers commissioned by Educational Testing Services as the TOEFL publisher investigating TOEFL listening item difficulty did not address the issue of the relative difficulty of the two spoken language types (e.g. Freedle & Kostin, 1999; Kostin, 2004; Nissan et al., 1996). Regrettably, such small number of research will provide insufficient understanding for developers and users of listening comprehension tests with regard to test content and intended test difficulty level (Papageorgiou et al., 2012:376) and for FL teachers concerning the specific listening interventions (Rost, 2007:106).

The small body of research as to the comparison of monolog and dialog texts has also been worsened by the inconclusive results. Among them, Read (2002) indicated that participants who listen to monolog texts outperformed those who listen to dialog texts of the same content discussed by three speakers. Nevertheless, as Read argues, the difference was possibly due to the unscripted dialog texts, uncontrolled speech rate, and a practice effect of previous monolog tasks.

Significant conclusion could not be drawn in two other studies either. Firstly, it occurred when Brindley and Slatyer (2002) investigated whether presenting the same information in the form of a dialogue resulted in any variation in listening performance. In this case, a dialog version was created from a monolog text and designed to include more redundancy and more fillers. Brindley and Slatyer (2002) put forward that the uncontrolled speech rate of one speaker in the dialog might invalidate “any potentially ‘easifying’ effects of the other factors” (p. 388). Secondly, it happened when Papageorgiou et al. (2012) rigorously analyzed the listening performance on three pairs of stimuli consisting

of monologs and dialogues with identical content and vocabulary. However, they found partial support only to the hypothesis that dialog text might be easier than identical monolog one.

As shown above, the small body of research as to the comparison of monolog and dialog texts has provided insufficient results. Furthermore, it has not yet been established how the origins of speech affect listening comprehension of the two spoken language types as within framework of the present study. In light of the two variables, it can thus be conceivably hypothesized that the dialogs and monologs moderate FL listening comprehension of the synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers. The speech origin and spoken language type are somewhat intertwined with the FL learners' listening comprehension (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1 The interplay of Origin and Type on FL Listening Comprehension.

With this in mind, this study was conducted for the purposes of making a comparison among three speech origins exposed to three groups and another one between two spoken language types provided to all groups along with studying the interaction between speech origins and spoken language types in terms of FL listening comprehension test scores. Attempting to shed light upon this issue, the present study helps widen the understanding of the comparative difficulty of dialog and monolog texts delivered by a speech synthesizer along with native and nonnative speakers.

1.2 Research Questions

The comparative comprehension of synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers, the comprehension of the three speech origins across dialogs and monologs, and the comparative comprehension of the two spoken language types in terms of FL listening comprehension test scores raise the following questions:

1. Do students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer perform the same as those listening to natural speech by native speakers?
2. Do students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer perform the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers?
3. Do students listening to natural speech by native speakers perform the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers?
4. Does students' comprehension of synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer, natural speech by native speakers, and natural speech by nonnative speakers depend on whether the spoken language type is a dialog or monolog?

5. Do students perform better when listening to dialogs than when listening to monologs?

Therefore, the objective of this study was to examine the effect of speech origins on foreign language listening comprehension across different spoken language types as measured by performance on a FL listening comprehension test. Given the research outcome, the Significance of the Study deals with how the present study could provide substantial new insight.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study can be significant for FL literature for the following reasons. In terms of the speech origins, it is conceivably of importance in that it helps provide quantitative evidence for the issue of the use of natural speech by nonnative speakers and synthetic speech in listening comprehension tests. While there is nothing in the literature to support the use of natural speech by native speakers as the most effective method of assessing listening comprehension, current opinion suggests the opposite. This research would seem to weaken the prevailing theory that natural speech by native speakers is significantly better for FL learners' listening comprehension.

The perspectives of cross-linguistic speech and World Englishes have also established the need for research into the effect, or lack thereof, of natural speech by native and nonnative speakers along with synthetic one on FL listening comprehension. This study explored the role of linguistic background by examining the validity of the interlanguage speech intelligibility benefit for talker whose native language was Indonesian. The results appear to disapprove that such

benefit exists for Indonesian listeners. Specifically, this study could not provide some evidence that a shared phonological system in terms of matched interlanguage speech intelligibility applied to Indonesian learners of EFL.

Furthermore, in terms of spoken language types, the significance of the study presumably lies in the fact that current research as to the relative comprehension of dialog and monolog aural texts in the FL context has not only been small in number but also inconclusive in result. On the other hand, spoken dialogs and monologs are inseparable from the current practice of FL learning and testing. The findings, in turn, are intended as a contribution to the FL literature by providing quantitative evidence of the effect of the two types of spoken language on FL listening comprehension. The evidence has favored the collaborative theory of communication of which dialogs deliver information better than monologs in the context of FL education.

The inseparability of speech origins and spoken language types seems tempting to investigate in terms of their separate and combined effects on FL listening comprehension. This study would be among the first attempts to understand how the two variables intertwined. The results that seem to suggest that the speech origins and spoken language types were not mutually dependent could enhance the understanding of spoken foreign language, thereby contributing to the collective knowledge in the field of FL education.

The better understanding of the equivalent comprehension of the three speech origins and the better comprehension of dialogs would be fruitful for the FL enterprise. Such essential understanding helps empower FL teachers to provide a specific listening intervention such as by manipulating complexity of listening

input and providing diverse listening input through the use of a speech synthesizer. For developers of listening comprehension tests, the findings shed light upon the issues of test content and intended test difficulty level. FL learners themselves could not only make meaningful listening choices but also simplify and enrich listening inputs beyond the classroom in which they have little opportunity for guided practice. In addition, this research helps to illuminate an alternative speech origin in classroom applications and other surrounding issues.

The present study may also find its significance in the field of digital speech technology in general and CALL/SLaTE in particular. Focusing on the comprehension through “black-box” testing (Taylor (2009:522-3) in which the researcher had no knowledge of how the system operates, this investigation differs from other evaluations. It is reasonably ripe for the multidisciplinary approach to evaluate the quality of TTS output and the interplay among varied variables on the FL listening comprehension. This study has attempted to broaden not only current knowledge of the comprehension of TTS system for the sake of TTS technology development itself but also the relatively equivalent comprehension of SS in comparison with natural speech by native and nonnative speakers when delivering dialog and monolog texts in the context of FL teaching and learning. Therefore, this study reports to the TTS and CALL developers the use of a concatenative speech synthesizer in another area for which the TTS software is not mainly designed. Based on this study, they can make relatively progress toward, for example, the user-friendliness of dialog SS generation.

The evidence was generated from FL learners in which little formal research had been done into not only listening comprehension but also the use of

SS. Since FL learners are the potential users of TTS technology, it is of importance to explore the use of speech synthesizer in the context of FL teaching, in particular FL listening instruction to which audio technology is closely related. In this case, the teachers, curriculum developers, and book authors' use of TTS software can avoid the negligence of listening instruction due to listening materials hardly produced and distributed.

To sum up, the study is among the first attempts to fill in the gaps in the literature relating to three speech origins and two types of spoken language as passage characteristics in FL listening comprehension. This endeavor could arguably heighten the understanding of the topics and shed further light on them.

1.4 Definition of the Key Terms

The following definitions are provided to ensure uniformity and understanding of these terms throughout the study.

Foreign Language Listening Comprehension is the score gained by a participant taking an EFL language listening comprehension test that shows the ability to understand the main detail in short spoken utterances and to extract specific information from extended spoken texts by one or two speakers giving or exchanging information.

Speech Origins are three different origins of input for an EFL listening comprehension test. The first origin is the talent voices of English native speakers employed by a test publisher. They learn English language as children and continue to use it fluently as a dominant language. Furthermore, the second origin is Indonesian nonnative speakers of English. They learn English wherein it is not

a widely used medium of communication in their daily lives. The last origin is a concatenative speech synthesizer. It synthesizes speech-like sounds from printed text input by concatenating units of speech, such as the phonemes or some other similarly short segments of speech modeled by a voice talent in carefully constructed carrier phrases and stored in a database in the form of either waveform-coded or parametrically coded signals. In other words, the speech is generated by joining small pieces of digitally recorded human speech. In this study, the speech origins are to which the participants are grouped.

Spoken Language Types are two types of spoken language used in an EFL listening comprehension test. The first type is a dialog involving one female and one male speakers for the interpersonal and transactional purposes. Another type is a monolog by which one speaker, either female or male, uses spoken language for any length of time without an interruption. In this study, both of the spoken language types are given to all of the participants.

1.5 Delimitation of the Study

The characteristics that define the boundaries of the inquiry are determined as follows. Firstly, without denying the potential importance of other factors affecting FL listening comprehension, the speech origins and spoken language types are worthy of inclusion for this study. Secondly, all of the synthetic speech in this study was generated by a concatenative synthesis in which a new audio text was chained from instances of particular speech unit in the database of natural speech. The speech synthesizing process was then bound by the experimenter's level of expertise in running the speech synthesis software. Thirdly, the natural

speech by nonnative speakers was set to natural speech by Indonesian native speakers of English. Finally, in order to assure manageability of the collected data, the instrument used 3-option (graphical) multiple choice items and text/note completion and did not include dictation.

CHAPTER II

RESEARCH METHOD

This chapter deals with the research design, population and sample, instruments, data collection procedure and data analysis.

2.1 Research Design

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of natural speech by native and nonnative speakers along with synthetic one by a concatenative speech synthesizer on FL listening comprehension across dialogs and monologs. To further the investigation, a true experimental, posttest-only design was used.

In the design, threats due to participant characteristics could be eliminated in two ways. Firstly, each participant was randomly assigned to one of the three speech-origin-based groups. Secondly, the participants were used as their own controls in comprehending the two types of spoken language. In other words, all of the participants listened to both types of the spoken language. Therefore, the experiment consisted of a 3 (speech origins: natural speech by native speakers vs. natural speech by nonnative speakers vs. synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer) x 2 (spoken language types: dialog vs. monolog) factorial design with Origin as the between-subjects factor and Type as the within-subjects one.

2.2 Population and Sample

The target population was all of the students of English Language Teaching program at a state university in Malang, East Java province, Indonesia. The accessible population was all of the sophomores taking Intermediate Listening course as a required course. In terms of Origin, the objective of the course is to enable students to understand accents, whereas with regard to Type, the course is aimed at enabling students to comprehend implicit information in various types of spoken English texts (State University of Malang, 2014:39). Above all, there is reasonable concordance between the course objectives and the research instrument utilized which will be dealt in more detail in the Research Instrument.

A sample was then chosen on the basis of two considerations. To start with, the sample size was of paramount importance in order to risk neither missing important information because of too small sample size nor wasting valuable resources because of too large sample size. The sample size needed was determined using a power analysis and sample size program, *PASS* version 13.0.6 (Hintze, 2014). More details on the calculation of sample size and analysis of statistical power can be found in Appendix 1.

In the procedure of repeated measure analysis with 3 levels of one between-subjects factor (Origin) and 2 levels of one within-subjects one (Type), the univariate test used was the Geisser-Greenhouse Corrected *F* Test with $\alpha = .05$ and the minimum power was set to 80%. The analysis shows that 3 groups with 10 participants each listening to one of the three different speech origins (between factor) but same dialog and monolog texts (within factor) achieved 81% power to

test Origin factor when the actual effect *SD* was 0.47 (an effect size of .6). The design also achieved 99% power to test Type factor when the actual effect *SD* was 0.5 (an effect size of .8). To test the interaction between Origin and Type, the design achieved 96% power when the actual effect *SD* is 0.5 (an effect size of .8).

The sample size in this study also took into account of the different approach in testing the first three hypotheses, i.e. the formal equivalence testing. More details on this will be given in the Data Analysis. The calculation of sample size and analysis of statistical power utilized the same software.

Based on the results of the calculation of sample size and analysis of statistical power as summarized in Appendix 2, it is shown that an equivalence test of means using two one-sided tests on data from a parallel-group design with sample sizes of 18 in each group achieved 80% power at $p = .05$ when the true difference between means was 0, *SD* was 2.0, and the equivalence limits were -2.0 and 2.0. Based on the two power analyses, it was determined that the minimum sample size was three groups with 18 participants for a total of 54 participants.

The next step in building up the sample was to minimize a bias by selecting participants taught by the same instructor. All of the students from the instructor's classes were then invited to take part in the experiment by having one listening test comprehension tests. Distributed in three classes (Table 2.1), those who consented to the experiment on a voluntary basis were 64 students (44 females and 20 males) whose ages ranged from 17 to 23 with a mean age of 19.2 years ($SD = 0.92$). They have learnt English for an average of 10.8 years ($SD = 2.01$) in terms of formal education. Most of them have learnt EFL since they were seventh graders.

Table 2.1 Participants' Grouping and Characteristics in Three Classes

Class	Speech Origin			Age			Length as EFL learners (year)		
	NS	NNS	SS	Range	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
A	8	7	7	18 - 23	19.5	1.14	8 -14	10.6	2.02
B	7	7	7	18 - 20	18.9	0.44	8 -14	11.1	2.05
C	7	7	7	17 - 20	19.1	0.85	8 -14	10.9	2.05

Note: NS = Native Speakers NNS = Nonnative Speakers SS = Speech Synthesizer

All of the participants were naïve to the purpose of the experiment. Each of them was randomly assigned to listening to one of the three speech origins in their own class.

2.3 Research Instrument

To examine the effects of three speech origins on FL listening comprehension across two spoken language types, a FL listening comprehension test was administered to the participants. It is taken from Section 1 and 3 of Official Sample Test 1 Pearson Test of English (hereafter PTE) General Level 4 March 2011 version 1 (Appendix 3). The permission from the test publisher to use the test itself has been gratefully acknowledged (Appendix 4).

PTE General (formerly known as London Test of English) is officially intended for teenagers and young adults of all nationalities whose first language is not English (More details on PTE General including its validity and reliability can be found on Edexcel [2010]). More specifically, Level 4 is for young adults of 17 and over at which the participants take part in this study (More details on a guide to Level 4 can be found on Pearson Education [2011]).

The first part of the test is aimed at testing ability to understand the main detail in short spoken utterances. It includes transactional conversations, social

conversations, and public announcements. With regard to the spoken language types, it consists of four dialog and six monolog recordings with a single 3-option multiple-choice question (or complete a sentence) for each recording. It takes approximately 9 minutes.

On the other hand, the second part aims to test ability to extract specific information from extended spoken texts. The texts replicate real life situations that require accurate comprehension and transcription of key information such as taking messages or notes. In terms of spoken language types, this part consist of one dialog and one monolog recordings. For each recording, there are five sentences to complete. The approximate time for this part is about 9 minutes.

Clearly, a detailed analysis of the written and spoken materials (Table 2.2) including the readability of the test book, which also functions as an answer sheet, and the transcript shows that both the test book and transcript fit the participants. The readability statistics was obtained by running spelling checker of MS Word 2013 whereas the length and rate of the spoken materials were analyzed through the use of sound finder of Audacity 2.0.6., free, open source, cross-platform software for recording and editing sounds.

In this study, the reliability estimate of the listening comprehension test ($N = 64$, $M = 11.48$, $SD = 3.95$) was based on the computation of Kuder-Richardson formula 21, $K-R21 = .72$. This indicates that there was good reliability.

All of the listening tests for the three groups were essentially the same in the broadest possible aspects such as content, gender of the voice, number of replays, speech rate, pause length, allotted time and layout. They differed in terms of the speech origins only.

Table 2.2 Characteristics of Written and Spoken Materials

	Test Book		Transcript	
	Dialog	Monolog	Dialog	Monolog
$\sum$ Words	110	196	694	861
$\sum$ Characters	552	1,093	3,121	3,891
$\sum$ Paragraphs	21	31	35	16
$\sum$ Sentences	11	19	70	51
Length w/ pause (minute)	-	-	6.2	7.5
Length w/o pause (minute)			3.2	4.1
Sentences per Paragraph	1.1	1.1	2.0	3.4
Words per Sentence	8.0	6.7	9.8	16.8
Characters per Word	4.2	4.8	4.3	4.3
Rate w/ pause (wpm)	-	-	111.6	114.8
Passive Sentences	0%	0%	0%	0%
Flesch Reading Ease ^a	78.1	57.6	76.7	64.8
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level ^b	4.3	5.0	5.0	8.2

^a The Flesch Reading Ease score is rating on a 100-point scale and is based on average sentence length and average number of syllables per word. The higher the score, the easier it is to understand.

^b The Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level score is a rating based on US grade-school level. A score of 5 means that a fifth grader should be able to understand the passage.

2.3.1 Listening Comprehension Test by Native Speakers

The first version of the listening test was the original one delivered by two female and two male English native speakers. As a baseline, no modification was made to this version. It was given to the participants in the group listening to natural speech by native speakers. It took 17 minutes 9 seconds to complete.

2.3.2 Listening Comprehension Test by Nonnative Speakers

Another version given to the second group listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers was delivered by Indonesian native speakers. The speakers who provided the input for the second version of listening test were two female and two male juniors majoring in English language teaching at an Indonesian state university in Malang, East Java. At the time of study, all of them have passed a course of Speaking for Academic Purpose, the most advanced speaking course of the three compulsory speaking courses. It is designed to develop students' ability

at advanced level such as employing important language functions in presenting current issues (State University of Malang, 2014:39). They were recommended by their former teacher of the course on the basis of the criteria essentially the same as that used by Abeywickrama (2013:63) with some adjustments. Specifically, all of the voice talents were able to communicate effectively in general and perform communicative tasks competently but their speech was not considered native-like.

Without listening to original version, the chosen speakers were recorded reading the assigned roles in the transcript of Section 1 and 3 of Official Sample Test 1 PTE General Level 4 March 2011 (v1) (Appendix 5). The recording session was held at a recording studio at the university. Sony IC Recorder ICD-SX713/SX813 was used for the studio work. The recording mode was set to high-quality one, i.e. LPCM 44.1kHz/16bit with a frequency range from 40 Hz to 20,000 Hz.

All of the recordings were proofed. In proofing the recordings, it was determined that Indonesian language-specific pronunciation in the speakers' speech was considered acceptable such as the unaspirated /p/, /t/, and /k/ along with the occasional replacement of /f/ with /p/ in terms of phonology. Where necessary, rerecording was carried out to get speech that was more acceptable.

The experimenter used Audacity 2.0.6. to combine, monitor, and normalize the recording. In the editing process, with the first version as a control, each speaker's recordings were positioned in accordance with the assigned roles. Silences were generated to insert pauses between spoken sentences too. In addition, the speed, pitch, and tempo were adjusted to match the original version as faithfully as possible. The result of the editing process was then exported as a

new audio file of WAV (Microsoft) signed 16 bit PCM as the best type of audio file (Sha, 2011: 639).

2.3.3 Listening Comprehension Test by a Speech Synthesizer

In the third version, the input for the listening test was generated by a concatenative speech synthesizer from the same transcript used for the second version. The last version was given to the third group listening to synthetic speech. The software used to produce this version was Voice Reader® Studio 15 (Linguatex, 2014). It was chosen due to, above all, the researcher's familiarity. In addition, it could synthesize speech of close resemblance to human voice and/or create audio files for publication using its variety of settings options such as sound effects, speakers, languages, pause, pronunciation correction, volume, pitch, and speed.

In the Option dialog box of the Voice Reader® Studio 15 window, the parameter of language was set to English (United Kingdom) and that of volume was adjusted to 100. Two female narrator profiles were created with the same speech speed of 100 but different speech pitches of 140 and 150 respectively. Next, two male narrator profiles were created. The first male narrator profile one had a speech speed of 100 and a speech pitch of 100 whereas the second one had a speech speed of 85 and a speech pitch of 120.

After creating and saving the profiles, the transcript was put on the application window. Some command tags were entered into the transcript to modify speech characteristics and to insert pauses. For the roles played by a certain narrator profile, for example, the name of the narrator profile was entered

into the transcript within square brackets by selecting the narrator profile from the context menu via the [Profilename] command. The entire transcript was exported or converted into an audio file format of WAV PCM 22050 kHz 16 Bit Mono. Finally, the result of the conversion was edited as for the second version.

2.3.4 Scoring

The scoring of the listening comprehension test was fully compliant with the Score Guide designed by Pearson Education (2012a:3-6). All of item types were marked as either correct or incorrect based on the answer key (Appendix 6). Each correct answer had a weighting of 1 score point. A maximum of 20 score points could be achieved in the listening comprehension test. However, given the different numbers of dialog and monolog items, i.e. 9 dialog and 11 monolog items, the maximum score points on each spoken language type was different. To make a more meaningful comparison, scores on dialog and monolog items were converted into percentage. Therefore, each correct answer had a weighting of 1.1 for the dialog items whereas for the monolog ones it had a weighting of 0.9.

Two raters scored the listening comprehension test. To achieve consistency in scoring, a set of score guide and answer key was given to each rater. Scores did not vary more than 1% between the raters. Cronbach coefficient alphas for the two sets were both .99.

2.4 Data Collection

The experiment was carried out at a computer-based language laboratory of the university, with the three classes taking the test at different times according

to their regular class schedule. The laboratory is always used for listening courses. Upon entering the laboratory, all participants in each class were randomly assigned to one netbook equipped with its own set of headset. All of the netbooks and headsets were the same in terms of model/specification and manufacturer. In each computer, one version of the listening test had previously been installed. Before putting headsets on, the participants heard an Indonesian brief verbal instruction on what they needed to do during the experiment. The verbal instruction was based on the written one on the test book with some modifications.

After the participants understood it well, they were asked to put on the provided headsets. They were also told to try out the computers and the headsets. Any participant who had found the headset out of order was asked to replace it with one of the extra headsets provided for a state of emergency. While trying out the equipment, the participants played a sample aural text of 10 sentences in the speech origin of the listening test they took. Besides familiarizing themselves with the speech origin, the participants were permitted to adjust the volume level of the headsets to a comfortable listening level.

Afterwards, they were asked to open the stimuli saved in a certain drive of each netbook and to play it using Windows Media Player. They completed the listening comprehension test simultaneously. For the first part, in approximately 9 minutes, after listening once to four dialog and six monolog recordings, the participants answered a single 3-option multiple choice question (or complete a sentence) for each recording. They put a cross in the box next to the correct answer on the test book. For the second part, in approximately 9 minutes, after

listening twice to one dialog and one monolog recordings, the participants completed a text or notes for each recording using the information heard. There were ten gaps to complete; five sentences per text type. The data collection proceed very much in the same way as indicated in comprehensive information on the preparation and processes of administering the test proposed by Pearson Education (2012b).

In line with it, two graduate students of the university assisted in the data collection on a voluntary basis. They also acted as the invigilators. They were trained to prepare and operate the computer-based audio equipment, to ensure that all of the participants were able to do the listening test as well as possible, and to solve some possible problems such as a blackout. As the netbooks in the laboratory were networked to a computer console, the instructor, who also acted as an invigilator, set the stimuli so that the participants were not able to pause and repeat the stimuli.

2.5 Data Analysis

This section presents a description of data analysis. It covers two stages of data analysis, i.e. data preparation and analysis.

2.5.1 Data Preparation

The data analysis begun with the preparation of a codebook summarizing all of the instructions used to convert the information from each participant into a format understood by the statistical analysis program utilized in this study, i.e. *PASW Statistics* Release 18.0.0., also known as SPSS. For example, Origin

variable was defined and labelled as 'speech_origins' with a coding instruction of 1, 2, and 3 for natural speech by native speakers, natural speech by nonnative speakers, and synthetic speech by a concatenative speech synthesizer respectively.

The next stage was to prepare a data file for analysis. After the data file had been created, the information from the experiment such as the scores of the listening comprehension test was entered in a format previously defined in the codebook. The data were checked for errors. When found, the error in the data file was corrected.

2.5.2 Data Analysis

To answer all of the research questions, the participants' listening comprehension test scores were submitted to a mixed design ANOVA. The procedure used for the statistical analysis of Repeated Measures of General Linear Models was as described by Field (2009). For all of the statistical analyses, unless otherwise stated, all results are reported as significant at $p < .05$ and all 95% Confidence Intervals are reported in square brackets. The magnitude of each effect size (partial η^2 or η^2_{partial}) as reported by SPSS Release 18.0.0. was classified in accordance with the 1988 Cohen's guidelines summarized by Larson-Hall (2010:119)

Before the results of the mixed between-within subjects ANOVA were analyzed, the general assumptions underlying ANOVA along with the assumptions of homogeneity of intercorrelations and sphericity had been explored to examine whether they were markedly violated. In exploring the assumptions, the homogeneity of intercorrelations are reported as significant at $p < .001$. The

assumptions are met when the results of assumption testing are not statistically significant.

Firstly, to ascertain that the distribution of each origin-based group in comprehending each spoken language type did not deviate from a comparable normal distribution, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was performed. Secondly, to see if the data violated the assumption of homogeneity of variances, the Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances was checked. In addition, to examine whether the pattern of intercorrelations among the levels of Type was the same for each of the levels of Origin, Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices was checked. Lastly, to assess the assumption of sphericity in which the variance of the population difference scores for any two conditions were the same as the variance of the population difference scores for any other two conditions, Mauchly's Test of Sphericity was used.

When the numerical exploration of assumptions was satisfied, the ANOVA proceeded. Otherwise, robust methods based on trimmed means and M-estimators would have been used as described by Field et al. (2012). In this case, different software would have been run, i.e. *R*, a free software environment for statistical computing and graphics.

Since the first three research questions were concerned with whether the comparisons of pairs of speech origin means were small enough so that the three origin-based groups were considered equivalent/similar, equivalence testing was used. The test followed no significant main effect of Origin found in the mixed between-within subjects ANOVA.

The use of the traditional null hypothesis significance test results in incorrect conclusions because an insignificant result does not mean that equivalency can be concluded and the concept of equivalence is ill-defined (Walker & Nowacki, 2010:194). The equivalence testing method in this study followed what was described by Rusticus and Lovato (2011).

At the beginning, prior to statistical testing, equivalence was operationalized. The equivalence itself was defined as “the minimum difference between two groups that would be important enough to make the groups nonequivalent” (Rogers et al., 1993:554). Rusticus and Lovato (2011:2) noted that $\pm 20\%$ appeared to be the most commonly used standard for equivalence intervals in the areas of bioequivalence and social science. In this study, however, a more cautious approach was taken to set the interval confidence. Based on the possible total score points of the above listening comprehension test, the equivalence interval for the present study was $\pm 10\%$ or 2 score points between groups (Group 1-Group 2, Group 1-Group 3, Group 2-Group 3) as used in the calculation of sample size and analysis of statistical power in the Population and Sample.

Secondly, the same procedure of Repeated Measures of General Linear Models were conducted to investigate the group differences and to calculate the 90% confidence intervals on the pair wise mean group differences using a Games-Howell post-hoc test. The 90% confidence intervals were used to test whether the mean group differences were within the equivalence intervals. If the confidence intervals were within the equivalence intervals, equivalency was concluded.

Returning to the mixed between-within subjects ANOVA for the conventional Null Hypothesis Significance Testing (NHST), because no

significant interaction was observed, the main effects for Origin and Type were examined. On the other hand, had a significant interaction been obtained on which the interpretation of findings was primarily based, the simple effect of Origin within levels of Type and that of Type within levels of Origin would have been examined. Such more complex analyses are available with the SPSS syntax language only. The steps to follow are as described by Field (2006).

CHAPTER III

RESULTS

In this chapter, findings of the study are presented. They are elaborated in reference to the research questions.

3.1 Comparability Analysis of Speech Origins

The first three research questions deal with the effects of speech origins on foreign language listening comprehension. Drawing on a large body of research, it was conceivably hypothesized that students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer performed the same as those listening to natural speech by native speakers; that students listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer performed the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers; and that students listening to natural speech by native speakers performed the same as those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers. To recapitulate, it was hypothesized that the three speech origins would yield equivalent listening comprehension scores.

On the test, the 21 participants listening to natural speech by nonnative speaker performed the best ($M = 12.00$, $SD = 4.04$, [10.16, 13.84]). In addition, those listening to natural speech by native speaker ($n = 22$, $M = 11.36$, $SD = 4.12$, [9.53, 13.19]) performed better than those listening to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer ($n = 21$, $M = 11.10$, $SD = 3.81$, [9.36, 12.84]). The listening

scores were then submitted to a mixed between-within ANOVA after the four assumptions underlying the mixed between-within ANOVA had been satisfied, i.e. normality, homogeneity of variances, homogeneity of covariance matrices, and sphericity (Appendix 7).

In spite of the mean difference, as previously anticipated, a mixed between-within subjects ANOVA with Origin (native speakers vs. nonnative speakers vs. speech synthesizer) as the between-subjects factor and Type (dialog vs. monolog) as the within-subjects factor yielded no significant main effect of Origin on the listening comprehension scores, $F(1, 61) = .28$, $p = .75$, $\eta_p^2 = .009$, power = .09. This indicates that if the spoken language type was ignored, the comprehension of three speech origins was not statistically different. The small effect size indicates that a mere .9% of the overall variance was attributable to this manipulation.

Bonferroni's post hoc pairwise comparisons were then used to compare the means of all combinations of pairs of speech origins. They reveal that no comparisons of pairs of means were significant (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1 Multiple Comparisons of Speech Origins

(I) Speech Origins	(J) Speech Origins	Mean Difference (I-J)	P	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Native Speakers	Nonnative Speakers	-0.32	1.00*	-1.82	1.18
	Speech Synthesizer	-0.13	1.00*	-1.37	1.63
Nonnative Speakers	Native Speakers	0.32	1.00*	-1.18	1.82
	Speech Synthesizer	0.45	1.00*	-1.07	1.97
Speech Synthesizer	Native Speakers	0.13	1.00*	-1.63	1.37
	Nonnative Speakers	-0.45	1.00*	-1.97	1.07

Note: * $p < .05$

However, careful attention must be paid in justifying that the groups of participants listening to the three speech origins performed the same in a foreign

language listening comprehension test. As stated before, in the case of a statistically non-significant value, equivalency testing was done to investigate whether the groups' listening comprehension scores could be considered equivalent/similar in which the equivalence interval was ± 2 and the 90% confidence intervals on the pair wise mean group differences used a Games-Howell post-hoc test. The equivalency test results indicate that the 90% Confidence Interval for all of the mean differences fell between -2 and +2 (Table 3.2). This indicates that the mean differences of all combinations of pairs of speech origins were small enough to consider equivalent.

Table 3.2 Equivalence Test Results for Listening Scores

(I) Speech Origins	(J) Speech Origins	Mean Difference (I-J)	<i>P</i>	90% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Native Speakers	Nonnative Speakers	-0.32	.86*	-1.63	0.99
	Speech Synthesizer	-0.13	.97*	-1.14	1.41
Nonnative Speakers	Native Speakers	0.32	.86*	-.99	1.63
	Speech Synthesizer	0.45	.74*	-.83	1.73
Speech Synthesizer	Native Speakers	0.13	.97*	-1.41	1.15
	Nonnative Speakers	-0.45	.74*	-1.73	0.83

Note: Equivalence interval = ± 2.00 **p* < .05

3.2 Interaction Analysis of Origin and Type

The fourth research question deals with the interaction effect of speech origins and spoken language types on foreign language listening comprehension. Since the generation of dialog synthetic speech has not been mature as fully as that of monolog one, it was reasonably assumed that dialog synthetic speech posed heavier processing demands than monolog one did. FL learners will comprehend monolog synthetic speech better than dialog one. This could lead to a hypothesis that students' comprehension of synthetic speech by a speech

synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers depends on whether the spoken language type is a dialog or monolog.

Contrary to expectations, no significant interaction effect was found between speech origins and spoken language types, $F(2, 61) = .46$, $p = .63$, $\eta_p^2 = .015$, power = .12. This indicates that the comprehension of the speech origins did not differ in dialogs and monologs. The small effect size indicates that a mere 1.5% of the variance was accounted for by the Origin x Type interaction. No matter from which speech origin the listening comprehension test was, all of the participants comprehended dialogs better than monologs (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 Listening Performance of the Three Origin-based Groups for Dialogs and Monologs

Figure 3.1 is revealing in several ways. Firstly, it pinpoints that the comprehension of the three speech origins was about the same. The differences in comprehension of the speech origins were merely random error. It also illustrates that the comprehension of the speech origins did not depend on whether the spoken language type was dialog or monolog. Furthermore, it shows how apparent the difference in comprehension was between dialogs and monologs. More details on this will be reported below.

3.3 Comparative Analysis of Spoken Language Types

The last question deals with the effect of spoken language type. Recent findings regarding the comparison of dialogs and monologs have led to the hypothesis that dialogs were easier to comprehend than monologs.

On the test, the 21 participants listening to synthetic speech performed better when the spoken language type was dialog ($M = 6.03$, $SD = 2.23$) than when that was monologs ($M = 5.07$, $SD = 1.74$). The similar pattern was also observed in the other two groups listening to natural speech by native ($n = 22$, $M = 6.11$, $SD = 2.56$ for dialog; $M = 5.25$, $SD = 1.84$ for monolog) and nonnative speakers ($n = 21$, $M = 6.24$, $SD = 2.06$ for dialog; $M = 5.76$, $SD = 2.48$ for monolog). On average, all of the 64 participants comprehended dialogs ($M = 6.13$, $SD = 2.25$, [5.55, 6.70]) better than they did monologs ($M = 5.35$, $SD = 2.03$, [4.85, 5.87]).

As hypothesized, the planned contrast reveals that the comprehension of dialogs was significantly better than that of monologs, $F(1, 61) = 12.94$, $p = .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .175$, power = .94. The large magnitude of the differences in the means

(mean difference = .77, [.34, 1.20]) indicates that 17.5% of the variance in the listening comprehension test scores is explained by Type factor.

3.4 Summary

Taken together, the results of data analysis investigating the effects of speech origins (Appendix 8) indicate five findings. First, FL learners listening to synthetic speech performed the same as those listening to natural one by native speakers. Second, FL learners listening to synthetic speech performed the same as those listening to natural one by nonnative speakers. Third, FL learners listening to natural speech by native speakers performed the same as those listening to natural one by nonnative speakers. In addition, the results of data analysis examining the effects of the three speech origins across dialogs and monologs indicate no significant interaction between speech origins and spoken language types. The last finding as to the effects of spoken language types indicates that FL language learners performed better when listening to dialogs than when listening to monologs.

In the final analysis, the quantitative evidence responses to the first three research questions are “Yes” because in the listening comprehension test, all of the participants listening to different speech origins performed similarly. Intriguingly, the quantitative evidence response to the fourth research question is “No” because the speech origin the participants listened to did not affect their performance when listening to both spoken language types and vice versa. In response to the last question, another “Yes” is obtained because all of the

participants performed better when the input consisted of dialogs than when the input consisted of monologs.

CHAPTER IV

DISCUSSION

This chapter deliberates the findings of this study. After being summarized, they are interpreted and integrated into the existing body of knowledge to theorize and suggest extensions.

4.1 Principal Findings

As outlined previously, there were five plausible hypotheses for the separate and combined effects of speech origins and spoken language types on FL listening comprehension. The first three hypotheses deal with the effects of speech origins, i.e. synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers along would yield equivalent listening comprehension scores. Fourth, the comprehension of the three speech origins depended on whether the text was a dialog or monolog. Finally, dialogs were easier to comprehend than monologs. The results lent some support to the first three and fifth hypotheses, but no evidence was found to support the fourth one.

Because the separate effects of speech origins and spoken language types are not qualified by a significant interaction between the two predictors, the interpretation of the findings could be based primarily on the main effects of each predictor.

4.2 The Equivalent Comprehension of the Three Speech Origins

As was reported in the Results, examining the three groups' data reveals that the mean of the group listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers was the highest among the three groups. At the same time, it also shows that the mean of the group listening to natural one by native speakers was higher than that of the group listening to synthetic one by a speech synthesizer. Consequently, it is tempting to speculate about "matched interlanguage speech intelligibility" (Bent & Bradlow, 2003:1607) or, more precisely, "Interlanguage Speech Intelligibility Benefit for Talkers" for which "speech by non-native talkers is more intelligible to non-native listeners than speech by native talkers" (Hayes-Harb et al., 2008:665). In addition, the least mean gained by the group listening to synthetic speech could have possibly been explained by the "youngest" speech origin's lack of accurate representation of prosodic cues as reported by Paris et al. (2000:429). Thus, the common sense notion that speech origins might affect foreign language listening comprehension appears to be supported.

The temptation to conclude at a glance from the mean difference seems very hard to resist. However, it is not yet known whether the difference is significant and can be interpreted as important. Such a rough estimate of the effects of speech origins thus cannot be emphasized too much except for describing a statistical model of the center of a score distribution.

Further analysis is consequently required to determine exactly how the speech origins affect foreign language listening comprehension. In this case, as was noted in the Results, all of the listening scores were submitted to a mixed

between-within ANOVA to test whether group means did differ significantly. The results of the mixed between-within ANOVA are thus highlighted.

In line with the first three hypotheses, the results were generally consistent with expectations of the mean comparisons among the three speech origins found to be equivalent. Synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers yielded an equivalent level of listening comprehension in a FL context. Specifically, the mean differences among the listening comprehension test scores obtained by the three groups listening to three different speech origins were small enough so that the three speech origins were considered comparable.

The result of this study also indicates that presenting synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer and natural one speech by native speakers had no significant difference in the participants' perceptual performance. This fits well with Hirai and O'ki (2011) who found that the comprehension of synthetic speech by a Japanese speech synthesizer of English was similar to that of natural speech regardless of the difficulty level of the aural texts. When the data presented here are combined with the results of Hirai and O'ki (2011), there is solid evidence that synthetic speech by a concatenative speech synthesizer has been relatively comparable to natural speech by native speakers due to the onward march of technological progress in the field of spoken language technology.

In this study, no significant mean difference was also found between the participants listening to natural speech by native speakers and those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers. The result reaffirms previous research (see Abeywickrama, 2013:64-5) reporting neither significant performance difference

between the test takers listening to American English native speakers and those listening to nonnative ones nor significant interaction between the talkers' and the listeners' native language. Previous studies also have shown that English speech by native speakers did not continually hinder EFL listeners' comprehension success and that the shared linguistic backgrounds did not constantly benefit their listening comprehension either (Barlow, 2009; Harding, 2011; Hayes Harb et al., 2008; and Major et al., 2002, 2005).

As reported earlier, synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer is equivalent to natural one by native speakers and natural speech by native speakers is comparable to natural one by nonnative speakers for the participants of EFL learners. Fortunately, the logic behind $a = b$, $b = c$, thus $a = c$ holds true in this study. Neither was the mean listening performance across the participants exposed to synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer and those exposed to natural speech by nonnative speakers found significantly different.

With respect to the power of this work, the evidence of no significant effect of Origins is not due to the lack of power. As was pointed out in the Research Method, the power analysis and sample size calculation had been performed before the experiment was conducted. Both the narrow 95% CI and small effect size statistics show that the lack of statistical significance is the result of the Origins having trivial effect on the participants' FL listening comprehension, not of the lack of sufficient power.

How did the three speech origins with distinctive characteristics result in an equivalent listening performance? Before reasoned speculation is offered, it is firstly important to recall that, in the context of this study, English speech

production by native speakers and Indonesian nonnative speakers differs very much as described by Yong (2002). Despite the fact that the English synthetic speech is generated by rejoining segmented prerecorded speech of trained native speakers, it is also fundamental to note that synthetic speech processing sometimes lacks accurate representation of prosodic cues as reported by Paris et al. (2000:429). The synthetic speech, such as it is, makes speech perception impoverished. On the listeners' side, they have lingual and cultural backgrounds in common with the speech origins of Indonesian native speakers only. Due to the FL context of the present study, it is well understood that there is a relative distance between the listeners' native language and the other speech origins' language. Apart from the noteworthy differences, the result is confirmation of the relatively equivalent comprehension of the three speech origins by the FL listeners.

A satisfactory explanation for this may be that the participants have orchestrated many factors to adapt the processing demands to each speech origin. The cluster of factors includes FL proficiency as the main contributor, native listening ability, metacognition, and motivation (Tafaghodtari & Vandergrift, 2008:109). More precisely, the major determinant of nonnative listening proficiency is linguistic knowledge (Andringa et al., 2012:73). The marriage of FL proficiency and native listening ability itself is consonant with Cutler's (2001:18) theoretical work, which argues that, listeners of a novel language combined language-universal and language-specific processes to make listening to any speech as efficient as possible. Within this perspective, the participants'

relatively similar lingual and cultural backgrounds made them use the two processes to adapt to one of speech origins in a roughly analogous way.

Besides the listeners' use of headsets making their attention undivided, the stimuli in this study shared certain similarities in the speech rate, text familiarity, and text complexity. Additionally, Drager and Reichle (2001:116) have shown that the four factors affect listening comprehension. The listeners themselves had level of FL proficiency and lingua-cultural backgrounds in common. The participants' no previous training and practice in listening the synthetic speech was not so detrimental that they comprehended the synthetic speech at a comparable level with other participants listening to the two "elder" speech origins. In this case, Papadopoulos et al. (2008:427) found that the training factor did not correlate significantly with the performance of listening to synthesized speech. This may mean the three speech origins were comparably adapted and processed on which their different characteristics did not make any difference significantly. It can be said that the relatively equivalent comprehension of the three speech origins was a mixture of the language-universal and language-specific processes in which the participants' similar level of tuning to FL input signals stemmed from the communalities of their lingua-cultural backgrounds and the text's complexity.

The experiment also provides considerable insight into cross-linguistic speech perception and World Englishes. If the terms intelligibility and comprehensibility could be used interchangeably and the synthetic speech generated by recombining small pieces of digitally recorded native speech might be classified as, to certain extent, native speech, the results reported here bring

light one issue in the study of comprehension of native and nonnative speech by nonnative listeners. Interestingly, the three origin-based groups' similar level of comprehension shows, to borrow Bradlow and Bent's (2007) "talker-independent perceptual adaptation" in which speech perception was flexibly processed to adapt to speech that deviated from or conformed to their native languages. As such, that nonnative listeners comprehended speech by nonnative speakers sharing their native language background the same as they did speech by the other two origins did not provide support for the prediction of an interlanguage speech intelligibility benefit for talker (ISIB-T). Although these results differ from some published studies (Bent & Bradlow, 2003:1606; Xie & Fowler, 2013:374), they are consistent with those of Hayes-Harb et al. (2008:671). The participants' relatively sufficient FL proficiency could account for the present lack of support for the ISIB-T and matched interlanguage speech intelligibility benefit in this study. The participants' drawing on such level of proficiency to parse the speech has helped free the dependencies of talkers and listeners.

The previous findings could also be interpreted as evidence pointing to a relative comprehension of the three speech origins. Nevertheless, no significant comprehension differences among the listeners exposed to two different speech origins were taken for granted to conclude that the speech origins under investigation were comparable (e.g. Abeywickrama, 2013:64; Hirai & O'ki, 2011:6). Previous research carried out in this area has drawn a conclusion of the comparative comprehension between two speech origins based on the conventional null hypothesis significance testing (NHST).

The incorrect use of NHST as a means of demonstrating comparability has been subjected to much criticism and has been vigorously challenged (e.g. Cribbie et al., 2010; Rusticus & Lovato, 2011; Walker & Nowacki, 2010). Rather than the NHST, the formal test of equivalence might have been more appropriate for demonstrating that two or more groups were equivalent/comparable.

Unlike previous work, the results of this study were further analyzed to examine whether the mean comprehension between the two groups in comparison were small enough to consider practically unimportant. In this case, what has been pointed out by Brown (2007) as “error resulting from not knowing what to do with null results” committed by L2 researchers could be rectified.

In this study, the conclusion that the two groups were equivalent are based on the formal test of equivalence, not NHST. For this reason, the insignificant results could be appropriately exploited. The strong point of this study thus apparently lies in the results that were more convincing in proving that the three speech origins were relatively comparable in terms of foreign language listening comprehension.

In interpreting the findings from this study, it is important to note the carefully controlled equivalence of listening test. The three groups were exposed to nearly the same materials in exactly the same manner. The amount of aural stimuli was precisely the same in quantity and content. The participants themselves were the stimuli were intended for in terms of content and age level. The single difference in the stimuli was that for the first group the stimuli were spoken in the forms of natural speech by native speakers, whereas for the second

and third groups they were delivered in the forms of natural speech by nonnative speakers and of synthetic one by a concatenative speech synthesizer respectively.

It is plausible that other disadvantages might have influenced the results obtained. To begin with, the input for natural speech by nonnative speakers was not provided by professional voice talents. As Campbell argues (2007), “the art of reading a text aloud requires considerable training, and very ‘few ordinary people’ can do it well” (p. 32). An additional possible source of drawback is that in running the speech synthesizer, the experimenter created four narrator profiles that differed in pitch only. The experimenter himself did the audio editing work for both speech origins. Although the nonnative speakers' limited training of reading aloud and the experimenter's restricted audio editing skills might had lessened the ISIB-T and the advantages of the advanced spoken language technology, such shortcomings were countered by a great deal of similarity among the three speech origins such as the speech rate.

The most striking result to emerge from this study is that the comprehension of the three speech origins is of relative equivalence. As Hintze (2014:460-1) points out, the definition of equivalence in medical research has been refined in recent years using the concepts of prescribability and switchability. From the standpoint, the existence of the three different speech origins in FL listening instruction can also be explored using the two concepts.

The former refers to the ability of, *inter alia*, curriculum developers to prescribe which speech origin should be used for FL education. It may be assumed that the stakeholders in the enterprise of FL education are all in favor of native speakers on the grounds of construct validity and acceptability. However,

the practice of FL education usually needs adjustment to suit a certain educational context. Therefore, the latter has a part to play. In a contextualized teaching learning process, switchability refers to the ability of practitioners in the field to switch the precisely prescribed speech origin with other available but pedagogically viable speech origins without adverse effects on FL learners. The prescribability and switchability of the three speech origins can also be framed in the term “fitness for purpose” introduced by Taylor (2006:56).

The implication of the present results for the use of TTS in the field of FL education is relatively encouraging. Although it still needs a great effort to make the synthetic speech level with the subtle complexities of natural speech processing, the state-of-the-art synthetic speech has been considerably acceptable. Those who object to the imperfections of today’s synthetic speech should take into account two things. Firstly, with regard to its insufficiency, given that very few native speakers qualify as voice talents/ models, “Yet we expect a perfect enunciation from a speech synthesizer!” (Campbell, 2007:32). Secondly, as far as the FL context is concerned, to use or not to use synthetic speech is not the question since FL learners “have long been exposed to far less authentic prosody delivered by non-native-speaker teachers, to which we should direct our initial concern” (Sha, 2011:640).

The exciting TTS technology itself is ready and waiting for FL education. Yamada et al. (2011) advocate EFL listening instruction using mobile devices because the so-called Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) increased the learners’ motivation, learning performance, and practicality. As regards the arduous development of listening materials in the form of natural speech both by

native and nonnative speakers, Sha (2013) has argued that TTS technology contributes very significantly to the ongoing implementation of MALL.

This experiment only focuses on the characteristics of the aural passages, whereas it might be important to include the learner variables as well. In fact, the inclusion of proficiency would be useful to examine the role of the learners' levels of proficiency on comprehending different speech origins. Further study is necessary to investigate to what extent the effects of speech origins are affected by levels of proficiency.

The framework of the current experiments can be also be extended in a long-term experiment. The future work can compare the effectiveness of listening materials of natural speech by native speakers and nonnative speakers along with synthetic one on the listening comprehension skills. The effectiveness of the three speech origins are then measured by asking the participants to do an internationally acknowledged listening comprehension test. Such empirical investigation will be fruitful in broadening the acceptance of other available but pedagogically viable speech origins in the realm of FL education.

As mentioned in the Introduction, so far no one appears to have compared the comprehension of three speech origins in a FL setting. The importance of the experiment thus lies both in showing the comparative comprehension of the three speech origins and the relative ease of application to day-to-day FL teaching and testing.

4.3 Comprehension of Dialogs: The Better of the Two

The experiment reported here was also motivated by the question as to whether dialogs were better comprehended than monologs. The result has further strengthened the fifth hypothesis that dialogs were significantly easier to comprehend than monologs were. In all conditions, the participants performed better when listening to dialogs than they did when listening to monologs.

One reasonable explanation for the better comprehension of dialogs is that the processing demands of dialogs were less heavy than those of monologs were. Within the framework of listening text difficulty (Rost, 2006:49-50), the foremost cause of the dialogs' less heavy processing demands can be due to the less difficulties of the dialogic items in the test. Some variables of the less difficulties of dialogic items could be interpreted on the basis of a surface analysis of written versions of dialogic and monologic items as previously compared in Table 2.2.

In case of the word count variable within the framework, the dialogic items had fewer words and characters. As the word count was lower, there was less text to process. This resulted in the less difficulty level of the dialogs in this study.

In terms of the text speed, the average speed of the speakers in the dialogs was 112 words per minute (wpm) which was lower than 114 wpm in the monologs. The slower speed means there were more pauses in the dialogs. Because there was more time for word recognition and parsing, the dialogs were less demanding than the monologs.

With regard to pause unit length, the average number of words per sentence (or pause unit) in the dialogs was 9.8 words per sentence that was lower

than 16.8 words per sentence in the monologs. The lower average indicates that the average pause unit was shorter. As the syntactic parsing for the dialogs was less than that for monologs, the dialogs were better comprehended.

Interestingly, the analysis of word count variable is supported by the scores of Flesch-Kincaid Grade level and Flesch Reading Ease. For the former, the dialogs scored lower than the monologs did. The dialogs' score of 5.0 means that a US fifth grader should be able to understand the dialogs whereas the monologs' score of 8.2 means that a US eighth grader should be able to understand the monologs. That the dialogic items were easier to comprehend than the monologic ones were based on the Flesch-Kincaid Grade level may also be an additional reason for the higher mean score of dialogs. Furthermore, that the less difficulty of the dialogs are also indicated by the higher Flesch Reading Ease score. The score is based on average sentence length and average number of syllables per word. The higher the score, the easier an aural text is to understand.

Another variable to note is concerned with individuals and objects involved in the aural text. Within the framework, Rost (2006:50) predicts that an aural text is easier to comprehend if it involves fewer individuals and objects because of fewer cross-referencing decisions to make. The results that the dialogs were easier to comprehend than the monologs, however, go against the hypothesis about the two variables. Female and male speech in the dialogs could explain why the dialogic items were easier. From an applied perspective, the use of female and male speech is the easiest solution to ensure easily distinguished speakers (Buck, 2001:166). Different-sounding speakers in the dialogs would ease working memory load. Each turn of the speakers might act as a cue and provide additional

processing time. The cues and additional processing time, in turn, could lessen the load on working memory.

On the other hand, the listeners had to handle longer tracks of speech by one speaker. As also shown in Table 2.2, the ratio of words and sentences for the monologic items stands at 861:51, which is denser than 694:70 for the dialogic ones. No having to take turn when speaking without interruption, the speakers in the monologic items used more complex syntactic structures. Such longer and more complex structure made the monologic elements more demanding to anticipate.

The two different-sounding speakers, accordingly, may also be included as another variable within the framework, i.e. object distinction. Clearly distinctive voices of the two speakers provide “clearer spatial and/or semantic boundaries between items being analyzed in short term memory” (Rost, 2006:50). Therefore, the existence of two different-sounding speakers in the dialogs could help ease the processing demands instead of taxing them.

In relation to the variable of pause unit length, the average number of words per sentence is 9.8 for dialogs that is lower than 16.8 for monologs. The shorter average pause unit has lessened syntactic parsing for the dialogs. Consequently, the dialogs were less taxing than the monologs.

Each variable within the framework cannot certainly be viewed as a separate entity. As a whole, the variables made the aural text difficulty of the dialogs lower than that of the monologs.

As noted earlier, the generation of dialog synthetic speech is not as mature as that of monolog one. That is why it was originally anticipated that dialogic

synthetic speech was harder to comprehend than monologic one. However, a post hoc analysis reveals that the participants in synthetic speech group comprehended the dialogs better than they did the monologs. This apparently better comprehension of dialogs even in synthetic speech group can be attributed to two possible factors. Firstly, the variables of the listening text difficulty in the dialogs benefitted the participants. Secondly, as mentioned in *The Equivalent Comprehension of the Three Speech Origins*, the participants in such similar level of proficiency were able to adapt to even the “immaturity” of dialogic synthetic speech. It would appear that the two factors effectively ruled out the advantage of maturity of monologic synthetic speech.

Such numerical approach for the written version of the dialogic and monologic items was relatively not satisfying enough to explain why the dialogs were better comprehended than the monologs. Another possibility is that the two speakers in the dialogs presented more perspectives than the only speaker in the monologs did. Compared to a single perspective in a monolog, more perspectives in a dialog increased the participants’ chance to adopt one of the perspectives (Fox Tree & Mayer, 2008). Even a single perspective when accepted (and repeated) by two speakers in a dialog is easier for listeners to comprehend than a perspective by the only speaker in a monolog (Branigan et al., 2011).

Regarding the effect size, the η_p^2 value of .175 indicates that the Type is causing 17.5% of the variance in this study. The effect of Type is statistically significant with a large effect according to the 1988 Cohen’s guidelines summarized by Larson-Hall (2010:119). The large effect is, therefore, of practical interest and importance.

The results reported in the present study could contribute some examples of the less difficulty of spoken dialogs compared to that of monologs when delivered by three speech origins in a FL context. They do not appear to corroborate previous results reported in current literature on FL education. Read (2002), for example, found that the audiotaped monologs were significantly easier than the audiotaped dialogs involving three speaker. However, the variables easing the listening text difficulty of the monolog were not due to the characteristics inherent in the monologs themselves. The monologs were easier because of a practice effect. On the other hand, dialogs were more difficult because they were unscripted and the speech rate was uncontrolled. Moreover, Brindley and Slatyer (2002:386) found that the dialogic version including redundancy and more fillers “was only marginally easier” than the monologic version. To some extent, the faster speech rate and longer text of the dialogic version ruled out the expected benefits of acoustic characteristics in the dialogic version. More recently, Papageorgiou et al., (2012) have been unable to draw any significant conclusions regarding the effect of dialogic versus monologic input on listening comprehension. Four out of six items with a difference of 0.50 logits and above were easier in the dialogic version because of the additional information by both speakers and the use of direct speech. Such results, nevertheless, were confounded by other two items that were easier in the monologic version due to containing more structured and explicit information.

How can the difference between the findings of the current experiment and previous research be explained? It might be at least some of the differences lie in the data analysis. In the last two previous studies on the effects of spoken

language types on listening comprehension, a Rasch-based analysis of the scores was carried out to know differences in item difficulty and the performance of the item options. However, Buck (2001:252) highlights the need to view a listening test as a whole. In this study, therefore, to ascertain whether the dialogs were easier to comprehend than the monologs, as a whole the scores obtained by the participants regarding each type of spoken language were submitted to ANOVA. Although the Rasch-based analysis provides a more detailed analysis of item difficulty, the ANOVA that is a relatively more established overall test of whether group means differ is more suitable to get more clear-cut evidence of whether dialogs are easier to comprehend than monologs.

Another possible difference is that in this study all of the participants listened to both types of spoken language. In their studies, Read (2002) and Papageorgiou et al. (2012) used some groups in which each group took different treatments in terms of spoken language types or contents. Since the participants in this experiment were used as their own control in comprehending both dialogic and monologic items, the individual differences were under control. Therefore, when the participants comprehended dialogs better than they did monologs, it was due to the characteristics of the two spoken language types they listened to, not other factors. In other words, random and uncontrollable differences among the participants were kept to a minimum so that the effect of the dialogs and monologs was more likely to show up.

Despite the discrepancies with previous work in the domain of FL education, the findings that dialogs were significantly less challenging than monologs appear to be well substantiated by a vast amount of scholarly literature

in psychology (e.g. Branigan et al., 2011; Fox Tree & Mayer, 2008; Fox Tree, 1999; Murfitt & McAllister, 2001; and Pickering & Garrod, 2004). The conclusion of the less difficulty of dialogic spoken language type as reached in this experiment would thus seem to be defensible.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to investigate the effect of the two spoken language types using a pair of well-designed matching dialog and monolog as done by Brindley and Slatyer (2002:386), Papageorgiou et al. (2012:380-1), and Read (2002:109-10). As is well known, developing well paralleled dialogs and monologs as in the context of this study is extremely hard. Consequently, the use of dialogs and monologs in an internationally recognized test as is becomes the most feasible way. It should be pointed out, however, a listening test in which dialogic and monologic items of the same content and vocabulary developed in such artificial way is rarely, if any, found in a natural setting, especially in a FL context. Evidently, a satisfactory rationalization for this is that a real-life listening test is to measure “the ability to understand a range of spoken text” (p. 5) by which “a more thorough sampling of the language area being tested” (p. 2) can be achieved (Edexcel, 2010). Had dialogic and monologic items in this study been effectively controlled and well matched, it still would have seemed unlikely to circumvent other factors such as lexical overlap between the options and the stimulus affecting item difficulty irrespective of the spoken language types as found by Papageorgiou et al. (2012).

Based on the results of this study, it is recommended that all of the controllable factors such as speech rate should be paid sufficient attention in such a way in the teaching and testing of FL listening. As such, the use of monologic

and dialogic aural texts is inherent in FL listening comprehension. The point at issue is what can be done to adjust the difficulty of dialogic and monologic stimuli to make them suitable for FL learners and testees.

The findings of this study have some implications for researchers of FL listening comprehension. Given that the findings are based on a limited number of dialogs and monologs, the results from such analyses should consequently be treated with considerable caution. As the results are promising, future research into comparative difficulty of dialogic and monologic aural texts should attempt to validate them by a larger number of dialogic and monologic aural texts.

Moreover, it is not yet known whether the comprehension of the dialogic and monologic aural texts of the same readability statistics, speech rate, pause unit and auditory length will differ. Naturally, there is abundant room for further progress in determining the relative difficulty of the two spoken language types in FL listening comprehension.

4.4 The Insignificant Interaction between Speech Origins and Spoken Language Types

It was the main purpose of the present study to draw attention to speaker- and passage-related factors affecting FL listening comprehension. Particular attention is paid to speech origins when delivering different spoken language types.

Surprisingly, this experiment did not detect any evidence for a significant interaction of Origin and Type factors on FL listening comprehension. Initially it was thought that Origin interacted with Type, primarily due to the heavier processing demands for the “immature” dialogic synthetic speech. However, a

closer inspection revealed that irrespective of speech origins the dialogic aural texts were less challenging than monologic ones.

The results of this study show that all of the three groups listening to three different speech origins comprehended dialogs better than they did monologs. This apparent lack of interaction between Origin and Type factors can be attributed to the roles played by spoken language types that are more significant than those by speech origins in FL listening comprehension. With the relatively equivalent comprehension of the three speech origins, the participants' comprehension differed significantly in dialogs and monologs. Each acoustic characteristics of dialogs and monologs could well be responsible for different perceptual challenges to the participants.

The results of this study suggest that FL listening performance among FL learners can be significantly affected by dialogic or monologic aural stimuli rather than by the speech origins. On the one hand, the very concept of prescribability appears to be difficult to get hold of, but on the other hand, it is still questionable whether the switch from native to nonnative speakers of a target language can be pedagogically applied in most cases (e.g. Saukah, 2009; Kikuchi, 2009; Nel & Swanepoel, 2010). Because of this, the 'youngest' speech origins i.e. speech synthesizers may be more effective and efficient for providing aural stimuli in the teaching and testing of FL listening. While waiting for synthetic speech perfectly matching up with human speech as the ultimate goal of the growing body of research into natural language processing, the existing synthetic speech has been considerably satisfactory for FL education in terms of accuracy, intelligibility,

comprehensibility, naturalness, and expressiveness (e.g. Handley & Hamel, 2005; Handley, 2009; Kang, 2009; Sha, 2011).

The existing TTS technology has been well equipped to help end users such FL teachers and test developers to focus attention on the range of variable auditory attributes such as sentence complexity. Some available features of TTS software allow the end users to modify synthetic speech in a variety of ways, to generate several different output languages, and to build more than one narrator profiles. Such features can help “provide specific interventions that will actually help our learners become better – more motivated and more curious – listeners” (Rost, 2007:106).

The apparent lack of interaction could be accounted for in part by the design of the experiment. As was noted in the Research Method, the experiment consisted of Origin as the between-subjects factor and Type as the within-subjects one. Cohen (2001:479) highlights that such pattern findings are due to the greater power of the within-subjects factor.

Returning to the issue of statistical power, the evidence of no significant interaction effect between Origins and Type is not due to the lack of power. As also described on the Research Method, the power analysis and sample size calculation had been performed before the experiment was conducted. Furthermore, the observed insignificant interaction had a small effect size. In this case, had this study lacked sufficient power to detect any significant effect because of insufficient sample size, the effect size would have been noteworthy.

The .9% and 1.5% accounted for by the Origin and its interaction with Type suggest that the individual main effect for Type, which accounted for 17.5%,

was the most important factor in this study. All in all, η_p^2 values indicate that the Origin, Type, and their interaction are causing 19.9% of the variance in this study (0.9 + 17.5 + 1.5). A whopping 80.1% the variance was accounted for by error variance. It indicates that more than four-fifths of the variance was not accounted for at all in this design. Such large error variance might be attributable to other variables excluded from this study. However, that the individual and combined effects of speech origins and spoken language types on foreign language listening comprehension have just accounted for less than one-fifth suggests that listening is indeed "a complex of factors" (Tafaghodtari & Vandergrift, 2008:100).

The findings of the insignificant interaction between the two factors on FL listening comprehension thus need to be interpreted with care. In future investigations it might be possible to extend the experiment in which both of the factors are examined as the within-subjects factors. Furthermore, it could be also important to add a between-subjects factor of listener characteristics such as FL proficiency level and working memory and/or of test taking conditions such as diverse time limits and control. Such further work may help in understanding the areas discussed here. Finally, a greater understanding of the findings could lead to a theoretical improvement in the complexities of FL listening comprehension and some practicable alterations in FL education.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This final chapter begins with the conclusion. It will then put forward some recommendations.

5.1 Conclusion

No one appears to have compared FL learners' comprehension of synthetic speech by a speech synthesizer along with natural one by native and nonnative speakers when delivering dialogs and monologs. Therefore, this study could add to the body of knowledge around the complexities of FL listening comprehension by determining the effects of the three speech origins on FL listening comprehension across the two spoken language types. The following conclusions are subject to the conditions and limitations of this study.

The most obvious findings to emerge from this study are that no comparisons of pairs of speech origin means were significant indicating all of the three speech origins have yielded an equivalent level of listening comprehension. The relatively similar level of sufficient FL proficiency could be responsible for the adaptation of the different acoustic characteristics. The diaspora of speech synthesizer, originally from the area of augmentative and alternative communication to the zone of FL education, has also been substantiated.

Another significant finding is that dialogs have been demonstrated to be easier to comprehend than monologs. Owing to the lower text difficulty, dialogs were easier to comprehend than monologs. The different characteristics of dialogs and monologs could be responsible for different listening performances.

Surprisingly, no significant interaction was observed between the speech origins and spoken language types of foreign language comprehension. The most likely explanation of the apparent lack of interaction is the roles played by different acoustic characteristics of dialogs and monologs were more significant than those by speech origins in FL listening comprehension. Another reason for this contradictory result can also be explained by the power of Type as the within-subjects factor that was greater than that of Origin as the between-subjects one. The lack of interaction thus did not supersede each effects of speech origins and spoken language types on foreign language listening comprehension.

The empirical findings in this study could consequently assist in a better understanding about the intricacy of FL listening comprehension. Taken together, these findings could be exploited in FL education where listening skills are of great importance.

5.2 Recommendations

The findings of this study have a number of important implications for future practice. In reference to the findings, the following recommendations are made for FL teachers, curriculum and test developers, as well as TTS developers.

This study has shown that the comprehension of three speech origins is of equivalence. An implication of this finding is that the three speech origins should

be taken into account in FL education on the basis of the concepts of prescribability and switchability. For classroom teachers of listening, if FL learners are believed to have to be exposed to today's real-life foreign language, then the native, nonnative, and synthetic speech should be provided to enrich the educational, linguistic experience of FL learners. If listening skills are neglected because of the incompatibility of the aural texts and the unavailability of a good model, TTS technology that has been pedagogically satisfying should be exploited to help FL learners become better listeners. For the FL curriculum and test developers, if the construct of listening is still believed to be synonymous with native speech in terms of the validity and acceptability, the dynamic reality of FL education in which the correct input is relatively insufficient for FL learners also deserves careful consideration. Within the framework of these criteria, the FL curriculum and test developers should encourage the practitioners in the field to include other available but pedagogically viable speech origins gradually to avoid adverse effects on FL learners.

Another significant finding to emerge from this study is that dialogs were more comprehensible than monologs. The current findings clearly support the relevance of different characteristics of the two spoken language types. For classroom teachers of listening, if the dialogs and monologs are universally considered the main types of spoken language, they should be inseparable from any listening instruction in accordance with teaching purposes. For the curriculum and test developers, if the universality of the two spoken language types is of significance, any listening texts should contain dialogs and monologs, to the extent that FL learners' listening comprehension could be developed and

facilitated. Furthermore, if the features of the two spoken language types affect the listening text difficulty, such features should deserve no little consideration for adjusting the level of difficulty of the input to make it suitable for FL testing purposes. For TTS developers, if the promising diaspora of TTS technology from the area of augmentative and alternative communication to the zone of FL education needs pedagogical acceptance, the quality of synthetic speech should be continuously improved with an emphasis on the dialogic synthetic speech. Furthermore, such acceptance will not be attained unless user-friendliness, especially for FL teachers and learners, is more seriously taken into account.

Taken together, the findings have not only theoretical values dealing with FL spoken language processing and communication but also practical ones because FL teachers, curriculum and test developers, as well as the TTS developers can manipulate both of the two predictors.

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Appendix 1

Power Analysis and Sample Size Calculation of Repeated Measures

Design Report

Term	Test	Power	n	N	Multiply Means By K	Std Dev of Effects (σ_m)	Standard Deviation (σ)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
B3(3)	GG F	0.8122	10	30	1.0	0.47	0.77
W1(2)	GG F	0.9865	10	30	1.0	0.50	0.63
B3*W1	GG F	0.9641	10	30	1.0	0.50	0.63

Term	Test	Power	n	N	Effect Size (σ_m/σ)	Alpha	Beta
1	2	3	4	5	9	10	11
B3(3)	GG F	0.8122	10	30	0.609	0.05	0.19
W1(2)	GG F	0.9865	10	30	0.791	0.05	0.01
B3*W1	GG F	0.9641	10	30	0.791	0.05	0.04

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Report Definitions

Term	:	The identifying label for the factor or interaction. For factors, the number of levels is also given in parentheses.
Test	:	Identifies the test statistic for which the power is calculated.
Power	:	The computed power for the term.
n	:	The number of subjects per group.
N	:	The total number of subjects in the study.
K	:	The means were multiplied by this value.
Std Dev of Effects (σ_m)	:	This value represents the magnitude of differences among the means for the term.
Standard Deviation (σ)	:	The random variation against which σ_m is compared in the F test.
Effect Size (σ_m/σ)	:	An index of the size of the mean differences relative to the standard deviation.
Alpha	:	The significance level of the test. The probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when the null hypothesis is true.
Beta	:	The probability of failing to reject the null hypothesis when the alternative hypothesis is true.

Repeated Measures Analysis

Results for Factor B3 (Levels = 3)

Test	Power	n	N	Multiply Means By K	Std Dev of Effects (σ_m)	Standard Deviation (σ)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
GG F	0.8122	10	30	1.0	0.47	0.77

Test	Power	n	N	Effect Size (σ_m/σ)	Alpha	Beta
1	2	3	4	8	9	10
GG F	0.8122	10	30	0.609	0.05	0.19

Results for Factor W1 (Levels = 2)

Test	Power	n	N	Multiply Means By K	Std Dev of Effects (σ_m)	Standard Deviation (σ)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
GG F	0.9865	10	30	1.0	0.50	0.63

Test	Power	n	N	Effect Size (σ_m/σ)	Alpha	Beta
1	2	3	4	8	9	10
GG F	0.9865	10	30	0.791	0.05	0.01

Results for Term B3*W1

Test	Power	n	N	Multiply Means By K	Std Dev of Effects (σ_m)	Standard Deviation (σ)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
GG F	0.9641	10	30	1.0	0.50	0.63

Test	Power	n	N	Effect Size (σ_m/σ)	Alpha	Beta
1	2	3	4	8	9	10
GG F	0.9641	10	30	0.791	0.05	0.04

Summary Statements

A repeated measures design with 1 between factor and 1 within factor has 3 groups with 10 subjects each for a total of 30 subjects. Each subject is measured 2 times. This design achieves 81% power to test factor B3 if a Geisser-Greenhouse Corrected *F* Test is used with a 5% significance level and the actual effect standard deviation is 0.471 (an effect size of .6), achieves 99% power to test factor W1 if a Geisser-Greenhouse Corrected *F* Test is used with a 5% significance level and the actual effect standard deviation is 0.500 (an effect size of .8), and achieves 96% power to test the B3*W1 interaction if a Geisser-Greenhouse Corrected *F* Test is used with a 5% significance level and the actual effect standard deviation is 0.500 (an effect size of .8).

Appendix 2

Power Analysis of Two-Sample T-Test for Testing Equivalence Using Differences

Testing Equivalence of Two Means Using a Parallel-Group Design

Power		N1	N2	N	D	SD	Equiv. Limit		Alpha
Target	Actual						Lower	Upper	
0.80	0.80454	18	18	36	0.0	2.0	-2.0	2.0	0.050

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Report Definitions

Target Power is the desired power value (or values) entered in the procedure.

Power is the probability of rejecting a false null hypothesis.

Actual Power is the power obtained in this scenario. Because N1 and N2 are discrete, this value is often (slightly) larger than the target power.

N1 and N2 are the number of items sampled from each population.

N is the total sample size, $N1 + N2$.

D is the true difference between the means.

SD is the within-group standard deviation for the two groups.

The lower and upper equivalence limits are the maximum allowable differences that still result in equivalence.

Alpha is the probability of rejecting a true null hypothesis.

Summary Statements

An equivalence test of means using two one-sided tests on data from a parallel-group design with sample sizes of 18 in the reference group and 18 in the treatment group achieves 80% power at a 5% significance level when the true difference between the means is 0.0, the standard deviation is 2.0, and the equivalence limits are -2.0 and 2.0.

This is the Pearson Test of English General Level 4. This test takes 2 hours and 30 minutes.

Section 1

You will have 10 seconds to read each question and the corresponding options. Then listen to the recording. After the recording you will have 10 seconds to choose the correct option. Put a cross (☒) in the box next to the correct answer, as in the example.

Example: This is an extract from

- A an announcement.
- B an advertisement.
- C a message.

1. The speaker says that a university education should be valued as

- A a means of personal fulfilment.
- B an opportunity for employment.
- C a useful contribution to society.

1

2. The speaker says many of his school lessons were

- A boring.
- B entertaining.
- C funny.

2

3. How does the boy feel?

- A shocked
- B furious
- C disappointed

3

4. Who are the speakers?

- A father and mother
- B brother and sister
- C husband and wife

4

Leave
blank

5. What is the woman's attitude to the loss of traditions?

- A regretful
 B realistic
 C pessimistic

5

6. Which word best describes the speaker's attitude?

- A appreciative
 B narrow-minded
 C critical

6

7. Who is the speaker addressing?

- A a group of actors
 B a group of business people
 C a group of students

7

8. How does the woman feel about helping at the wedding?

- A bored
 B reluctant
 C stressed

8

9. What disadvantage of the Indymedia website does the speaker mention?

- A the style of the writing
 B the quality of information
 C the advertising

9

10. What is the speaker describing?

- A emotional problems that teenagers experience
 B poor relationships between family and teenagers
 C reasons why youngsters spend time with friends

10

Q1

(Total 10 marks)

Section 3

12-16 You will hear an interview. First, read the notes below then listen and complete the notes with information from the interview. You will hear the recording twice.

Example: The World Today is a political magazine

12. Increase in magazine sales over the past 12 months:

13. The man does not regard the new online magazine as a

14. The content of the online magazine is more than *The World Today's*.

15. The man doesn't think relying on sales is a

16. The Internet magazine is funded through

17-21 You will hear a talk. First, read the notes below then listen and complete the notes with information from the talk. You will hear the recording twice.

Example: Speaker's occupation: (a) musician

17. He feels envious of people who learn an instrument but haven't had any

18. He finds it difficult to listen to music without it.

19. He also wishes he could more freely.

20. One vital necessity for success:

21. Main aim: to reach a point where you don't have to think about

(Total 10 marks)

12

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

Q3

That is the end of the listening section of the test. Now go on to the other sections of the test.

Appendix 4

Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@gmail.com>

Permission Letter to use for Pearson Test of English General Level 4 March 2011 (v1)

4 messages

Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@gmail.com>

Mon, May 19, 2014 at 12:33 PM

To: pltsupport@pearson.com

To whom it may concern:

I am completing a doctoral dissertation at the State University of Malang, East Java Province, Indonesia. It is entitled "The Effect of Speech Origins on FL Listening Comprehension viewed from the Text Types." I would like to ask for your permission to use Section 1 and 3 of Official Sample Test 1 Pearson Test of English General Level 4 March 2011 (v1) as one research instrument in my dissertation.

I also would like to receive information on the validity and/or reliability of the test.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours truly,

--

ABDUL SYAHID
Jalan Bromo 2 Blok D No. 18 Sampit 74312
HP 08125152537
HP 085390534666

-, **PLT Support** <pltsupport@pearson.com>
To: Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@gmail.com>

Mon, May 19, 2014 at 4:40 PM

Hi Abdul,

Many thanks for sending this through, please feel free to use Sections 1 and 3 from our Sample Test 1 for PTE-G L4, March 2011. We very much appreciate asking us for permission.

As for your final question, I'm just enquiring with our Test Development team as to where is the best lead to point you, will update you as soon as I hear back.

Warm regards,

Danny

PLT Support Team

Language Testing

E: pltsupport@pearson.com

T: +44 (0)845 543 024

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TRANSCRIPT

This is the Pearson Test of English General Level Four. This test takes 2 hours and 30 minutes.

Section 1

You will have 10 seconds to read each question and the corresponding options. Then listen to the recording. After the recording you will have 10 seconds to choose the correct option. Put a cross in the box next to the correct answer, as in the example.

Example: Listen to the man speaking. What is this an extract from?

M: Be one of the few, the proud, the Marines.

The correct answer is B

1. Listen to the woman talking. What does she say about a university education?

F: Since when was a university education like an apprenticeship? It's a learning experience. OK, it may get you a good job, but even if it doesn't, at least you will have expanded your mind and broadened your horizons.

2. Listen to the man speaking. What does he say about his school lessons?

M: I remember we used to mess around quite a lot when we were at school, just to amuse ourselves. A lot of the lessons were so dull that we had to make our own entertainment somehow.

3. Listen to the conversation. How does the boy feel?

M: What time do I have to be back?

F: No later than nine o'clock.

M: Really? But we won't have finished by then.

F: Well you'll just have to leave early then.

M: How come? It's not fair, that's not very late.

F: You've got school early tomorrow.

M: Oh alright then.

4. Listen to the conversation. Who are the speakers?

F: Oh come on, it's a family tradition. We've always done it, since we were kids.

M: That doesn't mean we have to keep doing it forever. Don't you think we've grown out of it now?

F: Maybe, but mum and dad still enjoy it.

M: Exactly - they think we still enjoy it but it's really for their benefit, not ours.

5. Listen to the conversation. What is the woman's attitude to the loss of traditions?

M: Don't you think it's sad that old traditions are dying out?

F: Well, I think it's just evolution really. I mean, if people want to carry them on - if they have some social value, then they'll survive. If not, so be it - it just means people didn't think they were worth keeping.

6. Listen to the man talking about traditional music. Which word best describes his attitude?

M: Fans of traditional folk music often seem to have this idea that anything modern is rubbish, which I can appreciate, because obviously a lot of it is. But it's a very narrow perspective to believe that traditional equals authentic, and is somehow morally better.

7. Listen to the man talking. Who is he addressing?

M: If you ever have to do an interview for the media, the first lesson is: don't think you can just make it up as you go along. Just because you're closely involved with the company every working day doesn't mean you can answer questions about it without any preparation or rehearsal. So do your homework on what kind of questions might come up.

8. Listen to the people speaking. How does the woman feel about helping at the wedding?

M: Do you think we should arrive at your nephew's wedding early so we can help out?

F: Not sure, we might be in the way.

M: I know what you mean, although I still think we should offer our services in some way.

F: Hmm, OK, I suppose you're right.

9. Listen to the man speaking. What disadvantage of the Indymedia website does he mention?

M: I get most of my news from the Indymedia website. It's open access, so anyone can post reports. That means you read informed reports written by the people who were actually involved, which are more likely to be true. The downside is that since it's a non-paying site you get these annoying pop-ups using persuasive language to try to get you to buy something online.

10. Listen to the man speaking. What is he describing?

M: Teenagers no longer want to spend all their free time with family. That is to say, they prefer the company of friends and this is, in the main, due to the fact that they are able to confide in people of their own age, who share their current perspectives and relate to their feelings in a way that the older generation cannot.

Section 3

12-16. You will hear an interview. First, read the notes below then listen and complete the notes with information from the interview. You will hear the recording twice.

- F:** Are online magazines really a threat to traditional magazines you buy in the shops? Here in the studio we have Jason Brown, editor of the long-established political magazine *The World Today*. Jason, this year saw the launch of a rival magazine broadly similar in content but online. Has it affected your sales at all?
- M:** Well, it's hard to be sure but I'd say no. We've had one of our best years ever. In fact sales have gone up by around 10% on last year's.
- F:** You don't see the new online magazine as a rival then?
- M:** No, not really. We're actually quite different in terms of content. We've always gone in for investigative journalism, whereas their site tends to have a lot of graphical content - cartoons, comic strips and so on. Another significant difference is where the funding comes from. We obviously rely on people buying a copy every month, whereas their site is free to anyone.
- F:** Isn't that a disadvantage?
- M:** It doesn't seem to be. In a way it's an advantage. Their revenue comes from advertising, so there may be some restrictions on what they can include. We're lucky not to have to rely on that, so we have the freedom to print whatever we like.

Now listen again

17-21. You will hear a talk. First, read the notes below then listen and complete the notes with information from the talk. You will hear the recording twice.

- M:** People sometimes ask me, as a professional musician, what's the best way to learn to play an instrument? It's easy to answer. Personally, I went the traditional route: I had piano lessons as a child, then eventually went on to study music at college. I seemed to have a basic talent for it, so it all fell into place for me, but in a way I still envy those people who are able to pick up music without formal instruction. For one thing, I find I can't just listen to music anymore; I always end up analysing it, which has killed the enjoyment a bit. There's another thing that I'd love to be able to do better, and that's improvise. I can do it, but I don't have the freedom to move outside accepted musical structures that self-taught players have. Whether you have lessons or teach yourself, the one sure thing is that you won't get very far without 100% dedication. The great guitarist Jimi Hendrix, for example, was self-taught, and some people imagine it came naturally to him, but his friends remember that they hardly ever saw him without his guitar, like an extra part of his body. What you're aiming at is physical memory, so that you don't have to be conscious of technique and what your fingers are doing.

Now listen again

That is the end of the listening section of the test. Now go on to the other sections of the test.

ANSWER KEY

Section 1

Example: B

1. A
2. A
3. C
4. B
5. B
6. C
7. B
8. B
9. C
10. C

Section 3

Example: political magazine

12. ten percent / 10 % / 10 percent
13. rival
14. graphical
15. disadvantage
16. advertising

Example: (a) musician

17. formal instruction
18. analysing/analyzing
19. improvise/improvize
20. (one hundred percent / 100% / 100 percent) dedication
21. technique / what your fingers are doing

SUMMARY OF ASSUMPTION CHECKING

1. Test of Normality

Tests of Normality

Speech Origins		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Dialog	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.152	22	.200*	.939	22	.187
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	.153	21	.200*	.931	21	.142
	Synthetic Speech	.136	21	.200*	.914	21	.066
Monolog	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.182	22	.057	.960	22	.495
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	.127	21	.200*	.936	21	.182
	Synthetic Speech	.128	21	.200*	.932	21	.149

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Summary Statements:

The listening comprehension scores for dialogs gained by the students listening to synthetic speech, $D(21) = 0.14$, $p = .20$, by those listening to natural speech by native speakers, $D(22) = 0.15$, $p = .20$, and by those listening to natural speech by nonnative speakers, $D(21) = 0.15$, $p = .20$ were all significantly normal. The scores for monologs by the first group, $D(21) = 0.13$, $p = .20$, by the second group, $D(22) = 0.18$, $p = .06$, and the third group, $D(21) = 0.13$, $p = .20$, were normally distributed.

2. Test of Homogeneity of Variance

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^a

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
Dialog	1.012	2	61	.369
Monolog	2.177	2	61	.122

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Design: Intercept + speech

Within Subjects Design: Spoken_Language_Type

Summary Statements:

Levene's test shows that the variances were equal for dialogs, $F(2, 61) = 1.01$, $p = .37$, and so were they for monologs, $F(2, 61) = 1.01$, $p = .12$. It can be concluded that the spread of listening comprehension scores was equal when the participants listened to dialogs and monologs.

3. Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices

Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices^a

Box's M	14.206
F	2.255
df1	6
df2	91519.709
Sig.	.035

Tests the null hypothesis that the observed covariance matrices of the dependent variables are equal across groups.

a. Design: Intercept + speech

Within Subjects Design: Spoken_Language_Type

Summary Statements:

Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices indicates that the six matrices $F(6, 91519.7) = 2.26, p = .035$, were roughly the same. It can be concluded that the pattern of intercorrelations among the levels of Type was the same for each of the levels of Origin.

4. Test of Sphericity

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^b

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Spoken_Language_Type	1.000	.000	0	.

Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.

b. Design: Intercept + speech

Within Subjects Design: Spoken_Language_Type

Summary Statements:

No significance value for Mauchly's test is due to the spoken language type as the repeated-measures variable consisting of two levels only, i.e. dialogs and monologs. Therefore, the sphericity is not an issue in this study.

SUMMARY OF MIXED BETWEEN-WITHIN SUBJECTS ANOVA

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Spoken Language Types	Dependent Variable
dimension1 1	Dialogs
dimension1 2	Monologs

Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Speech Origins	1	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	22
	2	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	21
	3	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	21

Descriptive Statistics

Speech Origins		Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Dialogs	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	6.1114	2.56184	22
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	6.2443	2.06472	21
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	6.0329	2.23967	21
	Total	6.1292	2.26739	64
Monologs	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	5.2500	1.83641	22
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	5.7586	2.47670	21
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	5.0662	1.73622	21
	Total	5.3566	2.02839	64

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure:MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable:Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	2110.482	1	2110.482	528.169	.000	.896
Speech Origins	2.274	2	1.137	.285	.753	.009
Error	243.747	61	3.996			

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure:MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable:Average

Source	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^a
Intercept	528.169	1.000
Speech Origins	.569	.093

a. Computed using alpha = .05

Estimated Marginal Means

Speech Origins

Measure:MEASURE_1

Speech Origins	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Natural Speech by Native Speakers	5.681	.426	4.828	6.533
Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	6.001	.436	5.129	6.874
Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	5.550	.436	4.677	6.422

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Spoken Language Types	Sphericity Assumed	19.025	1	19.025	12.937
	Greenhouse-Geisser	19.025	1.000	19.025	12.937
	Huynh-Feldt	19.025	1.000	19.025	12.937
	Lower-bound	19.025	1.000	19.025	12.937
Spoken Language Types * Speech Origins	Sphericity Assumed	1.346	2	.673	.458
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1.346	2.000	.673	.458
	Huynh-Feldt	1.346	2.000	.673	.458
	Lower-bound	1.346	2.000	.673	.458
Error(Spoken Language Types)	Sphericity Assumed	89.704	61	1.471	
	Greenhouse-Geisser	89.704	61.000	1.471	
	Huynh-Feldt	89.704	61.000	1.471	
	Lower-bound	89.704	61.000	1.471	

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter
Spoken Language Types	Sphericity Assumed	.001	.175	12.937
	Greenhouse-Geisser	.001	.175	12.937
	Huynh-Feldt	.001	.175	12.937
	Lower-bound	.001	.175	12.937
Spoken Language Types * Speech Origins	Sphericity Assumed	.635	.015	.916
	Greenhouse-Geisser	.635	.015	.916
	Huynh-Feldt	.635	.015	.916
	Lower-bound	.635	.015	.916

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source		Observed Power ^a
Spoken Language Types	Sphericity Assumed	.943
	Greenhouse-Geisser	.943
	Huynh-Feldt	.943
	Lower-bound	.943
Spoken Language Types * Speech Origins	Sphericity Assumed	.121
	Greenhouse-Geisser	.121
	Huynh-Feldt	.121
	Lower-bound	.121

a. Computed using alpha = .05

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source	Spoken Language Types	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Spoken Language Types	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	38.050	1	38.050
Spoken Language Types * Origins	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	2.693	2	1.346
Error(Spoken Language Type)	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	179.409	61	2.941

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source	Spoken Language Types	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Spoken Language Types	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	12.937	.001	.175
Spoken Language Types * Speech Origins	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	.458	.635	.015

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure:MEASURE_1

Source	Spoken Language Types	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^a
Spoken Language Types	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	12.937	.943
Spoken Language Types * Speech Origins	dimension2 Level 1 vs. Level 2	.916	.121

a. Computed using alpha = .05

Estimated Marginal Means**Spoken Language Types**

Measure:MEASURE_1

Spoken_Language_Type	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
dimension1 1	6.130	.288	5.554	6.705
dimension1 2	5.358	.255	4.848	5.868

Speech Origins * Spoken Language Types

Measure:MEASURE_1

Speech Origins	Spoken_Language_Type	Mean	Std. Error
Natural Speech by Native Speakers	dimension2 1	6.111	.491
	dimension2 2	5.250	.435
Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	dimension2 1	6.244	.502
	dimension2 2	5.759	.445
Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	dimension2 1	6.033	.502
	dimension2 2	5.066	.445

Speech Origins * Spoken_Language_Type

Measure:MEASURE_1

Speech Origins	Spoken_Language_Type	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Natural Speech by Native Speakers	dimension2 1	5.130	7.093
	dimension2 2	4.380	6.120
Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	dimension2 1	5.240	7.249
	dimension2 2	4.869	6.649
Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	dimension2 1	5.028	7.038
	dimension2 2	4.176	5.956

Post Hoc Tests

Speech Origins

Multiple Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

	(I) Speech Origins	(J) Speech Origins	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error
Bonferroni	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	-.3207	.60984
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	.1312	.60984
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.3207	.60984
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	.4519	.61689
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	-.1312	.60984
		Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	-.4519	.61689
Games-Howell	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	-.3207	.62249
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	.1312	.60556
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.3207	.62249
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	.4519	.60652
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	-.1312	.60556
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	-.4519	.60652

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3.996.

Multiple Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Speech Origins		(J) Speech Origins	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound
Bonferroni	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.000	-1.8221
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.000	-1.3701
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.000	-1.1806
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.000	-1.0668
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.000	-1.6325
		Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.000	-1.9706
Games- Howell	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	.864	-1.8345
		Synthetic Speech	.974	-1.3414
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.864	-1.1930
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	.738	-1.0245
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	.974	-1.6037
		Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	.738	-1.9283

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3.996.

Multiple Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

	(I) Speech Origins	(J) Speech Origins	95% Confidence Interval
			Upper Bound
Bonferroni	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.1806
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.6325
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.8221
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.9706
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.3701
		Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.0668
Games-Howell	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.1930
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.6037
	Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.8345
		Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	1.9283
	Synthetic Speech by a Concatenative Speech Synthesizer	Natural Speech by Native Speakers	1.3414
		Natural Speech by Nonnative Speakers	1.0245

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 3.996.

CURRICULUM VITAE

Abdul Syahid was born in Sampit, East Kotawaringin district of Central Kalimantan province, on October 4, 1970. He is the only child of *almarhum* H. Syukrie and *almarhumah* Hj. Rinti. He finished his primary education at SD Negeri Sampit II in 1983 and his lower secondary one at SMP Negeri I Sampit in 1986. He went to SMA Negeri 1 Sampit for his upper secondary education and graduated in 1989. He earned a bachelor's degree in English Language Teaching from Palangkaraya University in 1993. With the grant from the Government of East Kotawaringin District, he received a master's degree in English Language Teaching from Sebelas Maret University in 2010.

He began his career as a teacher of English at SMA Negeri 1 Sepang from 1995 to 1999. Since then he has taught at SMA Negeri 2 Sampit. He was also assigned to be the headmaster of SMP and SMA *Islam Terpadu Darul Ma'rifah* Sampit from 2010 to 2012.

He is married to Leny Mahdalena, a teacher of English at SMA Negeri 4 Sampit who has a Master's in English Language Teaching from Sebelas Maret University too. They have one daughter, Cattleya Asya Putri, and two sons, Rolihlahla Adhie Nugraha Asya Putra and Linus Osama Asya Putra.

Considering playing with his children as his main activity, he can be reached at abdul.syahid@gmail.com.